

Beyond graphene: Clean, hydrogenated and halogenated silicene, germanene, stanene, and plumbene

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Abstract

The fascinating electronic and optoelectronic properties of freestanding graphene and the possible inclusion of novel two-dimensional (2D) systems in silicon-based electronics have driven the search for atomic layers consisting of other group-IV elements Si, Ge, Sn, and Pb, which form similar hexagonal lattices and are isoelectronic to graphene. The resulting 2D crystals silicene, germanene, stanene and plumbene, referred as Xenos, but also their functionalized counterparts, e.g. the hydrogenated sheet crystals, named as Xanes, silicane, germanane, and stanane, are in the focus of this review article. In addition, halogenated Xenos are investigated. The consequences of the larger atomic radii on the atomic geometry, the energetic stability, and possible epi-

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taxial preparations are discussed.

In the case of honeycomb atomic arrangements, the low-energy electronic excitations are ruled by almost linear bands. Spin-orbit coupling opens small gaps leading to Dirac fermions with finite effective masses. The linear bands give rise to an absorbance of the Xenes determined by the finestructure constant in the long-wavelength regime. While for vanishing photon energies the excitonic influence is still an open question, saddle-point excitons and excitons at M_0 van Hove singularities appear at higher frequencies. After opening substantial fundamental gaps by hydrogenation, the absorption edges of the Xanes, silicane, germanane, and stanane, are dominated by bound excitons with extremely large binding energies. Other chemical functionalizations, but also vertical electric fields, yield electronic structures ranging from topological to trivial insulators. Even a quantum spin Hall phase is predicted at room temperature. The topological character and the possible quantization of the spin Hall conductivity are studied versus gap inversion, chemical functionalization, and Rashba spin-orbit interaction. The drastic changes of the electronic properties of Xenes with chemical functionalization, interaction with the substrate, and external perturbations, open future opportunities for tailoring fundamental properties and, therefore, interesting applications in novel electronic and optoelectronic nanodevices.

Keywords: two-dimensional material, interaction with substrate, Dirac electron, band topology, optical spectra, spin Hall conductivity

1. Introduction

In the year 2004 A. K. Geim, K. S. Novoselov, and collaborators experimentally exfoliated and identified graphene [1, 2], a two-dimensional (2D) single atomic layer of sp^2 -bonded carbon (C). However, already as early as 1947, P. Wallace predicted a theoretical band structure of this one-atom-thick crystal [3]. Moreover, in 1962 the research group of H. P. Boehm synthesized graphene flakes through reduction of graphene oxide (GO) dispersions [4]. The term “graphene” or “graphene layer” for a single carbon layer of graphite was officially first introduced by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry in 1995 [5].

The exfoliation of graphene [1] and the subsequent discovery of its unusual electronic properties [2] have led to an extraordinary interest from both academia and industry. Among the amazing properties are its 2.3% absorbance for long-wavelength light [6, 7], high Young modulus [8], and large thermal conductivity [9]. Its linear bands result in a remarkable electron mobility up to about $200000 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at room temperature [10, 11]. Free carriers in a graphene sheet show an anomalous half-integer quantization of the Hall conductance, providing a convincing proof of the chiral nature of these massless carriers [2, 12]. Because of its properties, applications of graphene have been explored in several areas, for instance, in high-speed electronic circuits, optical and photovoltaic devices, chemical sensors, and energy storage materials. A variety of proof-of-concept devices has been demonstrated (see reviews [13, 14, 15]).

Unfortunately, the character of a zero-gap multivalley semiconductor (no free carriers) or a semimetal (after doping), and the chemical inertness of

graphene, hamper the development and utilization of its full potential for nanoelectronics. Graphene lacks the electron transfer switch that supports contemporary silicon-based electronics. However, functionalizing graphene and manipulating its gap, the resulting new materials may be promising candidates for novel electronic technologies, within and beyond complementary metal-oxide semiconductors (CMOSs).

To keep the properties of a 2D crystal but overcome the limitations of graphene, researchers have explored various honeycomb analogues of graphene, such as the insulator hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) and semiconducting transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) MoS₂, WS₂, MoSe₂, and WSe₂. However, these materials significantly differ from graphene on the electronic density of states (DOS) and the degree of electronic confinement in normal direction. Moreover, these alternative 2D materials cannot be easily integrated with the current generation of electronic technologies. Therefore, elemental 2D analogues of graphene, which are based on the other group-IVA elements silicon (Si), germanium (Ge), tin (Sn), and eventually lead (Pb), are fast emerging as promising alternatives with predictions of high degree of integration with existing Si-based device technologies. This is obvious for silicene, because silicon is the most commonly used industrial electronic material, in particular for silicon-based integrated circuits.

This article reviews the emerging class of atomic sheets of elemental materials Si, Ge, Sn, and, in a few cases, also Pb with emphasis on their fundamental properties such as atomic geometry, electronic states, and optical spectra. The increasing spin-orbit coupling (SOC) and the possible sheet buckling along the group-IV elements open up a platform for researching a

novel quantum state of matter, a 2D topological insulator (TI) and the accompanying quantum spin Hall (QSH) phase. In the form of a (freestanding) hexagonal polymorph with some puckering of the atomic geometry, we will call the 2D crystals silicene, germanene, stanene, and plumbene. This denotation as Xenes follows that of graphene and is combined with the name of the element [16]. Only in the tin case we do not call the 2D crystal ‘tinene’ [17, 18, 19], but follow the community with the denotation ‘stanene’. It combines the Latin name ‘stannum’ for tin with the suffix ‘-ene’ used by graphene. Similarly, the term ‘plumbene’, derived from ‘plumbum’ and not from ‘lead’, is used in the Pb case.

From graphene one knows that chemical modification often gives rise to significantly different properties from the parent material. Such chemical functionalizations include various oxidation schemes, halogenation reactions, and hydrogenation. The latter represents the simplest possible approach [20]. Assuming no break of in-plane sp^2 carbon-carbon bonds, only one hydrogen can bond to each carbon atom. A fundamental gap opens in the center of the Brillouin zone (BZ) due to local rehybridization from sp^2 to partial sp^3 one. Indeed, the size of the gap is determined by the amount of chemisorbed hydrogen but, thereby, the gap formation is reversible [21]. An alternating but fully hydrogenated graphene is called graphane [22]. Chemical functionalization should also play an important role for other group-IV atomic sheets, in particular for size and BZ position of the fundamental gap as well as the strength of SOC. Among the thinkable functionalizations, hydrogenation and halogenation will be studied in this review article as the most important modifications. The fully hydrogenated group-IV analogues

are called silicane, germanane, and stanane [23], by analogy to their carbon counterpart, graphane. Because of significantly different electronegativities [24] and increased relativistic band structure effects, halogenated group-IV analogues are investigated in the context of topological properties.

The extraordinary features of the 2D group-IV layers, as well as their chemical derivatives, suggest their application in novel devices or in novel material combinations, e.g. 2D heterostructures. Consequently, suggestive headlines can be found in literature, for instance “Silicene may join graphene as wonder material” [25], “Is silicene the next graphene?” [26], “Will 2D tin be the next supermaterial?” [27] or “Could atomically thin tin transform electronics?” [28].

Summarizing, this article reviews the emerging class of 2D elemental crystals – silicene, germanene, stanene, and plumbene. In addition, their chemically functionalized counterparts due to hydrogenation or halogenation are investigated, all with emphasis on the fundamental properties. Atomic geometry and energetic stability are discussed with consequences for the synthesis of the 2D materials. The electronic structure, together with its sensitivity to the arrangement of group-IV atoms, kind of chemisorbed atoms, and external perturbations such as strain or electric fields, is a central point for many intrinsic properties. The chapter on optical response illustrates the fascinating electrostatics of monolayer systems and the influence of electronic confinement on excitons. Symmetry and SOC of clean and functionalized group-IV sheets are related to topological properties including the spin Hall conductivity. Future aspects harvesting manipulations of the electronic structure for electronic and optoelectronic applications are identified.

2. Atomic geometry and stability

2.1. Freestanding monolayers

2.1.1. Structure versus total energy

After the isolation of the single atomic layer of carbon, the graphene [1], there were speculations about similar 2D allotropes of the group-IV materials Si, Ge, and Sn (see Fig. 1). In particular, the option of honeycomb lattices beyond graphene fascinated the scientific community. However, graphite-like Si, Ge or Sn phases with intralayer sp^2 bonding and interlayer van der Waals (vdW) interaction do not exist [29]. Therefore, the preparation of Xenos by exfoliation is not possible, only a deposition on some sort of substrate, metal, semiconductor or insulator. Si (1.11 Å), Ge (1.22 Å), Sn (1.41 Å) and Pb (1.47 Å) possess much larger covalent radii than C (0.77 Å) [24], which promote sp^3 hybridization instead of sp^2 one. Indeed, theoretical predictions confirm the 2D hexagonal Bravais lattice with a lattice constant a , two group-IV atoms in the primitive unit cell but a layer buckling Δ in contrast to the planar graphene [30]. The space group is D_{3d}^3 ($P\bar{3}m1$) and the point group D_{3d} ($\bar{3}m$), which include inversion symmetry [31, 32]. The symmetry of graphene without buckling is characterized by D_{6h}^3 ($P6_3/mcm$) and D_{6h} ($6/mmm$). That means that the buckled geometry is formed at the expense of lowering the symmetry from the point group D_{6h} to D_{3d} [33]. Interestingly, the buckled graphene-like silicene is considered as reconstruction element in recent models of the low-temperature Si(111)7×7 surface [34].

Much data for freestanding Xenos arise from *ab-initio* calculations in the framework of the density functional theory (DFT) [35, 36] as implemented in various codes such, for example, as QUANTUM ESPRESSO [37], VASP

[38, 39] or SIESTA [40], where the Kohn-Sham (KS) wave functions [36] are expanded into a set of plane waves (PWs), projector-augmented waves (PAWs) [41, 42] and numerical atomic orbitals, respectively, up to kinetic energies of the order of 100 Ry. The used electronic configurations (Ne) $3s^23p^2$ for Si, (Ar) $4s^24p^2$ for Ge, (Kr) $5s^25p^2$ for Sn and (Xe) $6s^26p^2$ for Pb treat core electrons frozen in the nuclei but model explicitly the valence electrons with norm-conserving or PAW pseudopotentials. The effects of the electron-electron interaction beyond the classical Hartree term, exchange and correlation (XC), are treated within the local density approximation (LDA) [36, 43] or the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) according to Perdew, Becke and Ernzerhof (PBE) [44] or refined versions such as PBEsol [45]. In cases beyond the freestanding 2D crystals also vdW interaction [46, 47, 48] is taken into account.

The isolated (freestanding) C, Si, Ge, Sn, and Pb atomic layers (Fig. 2a) are simulated within a repeated slab approximation [49], basically a graphite-like superlattice arrangement with a large superlattice period L (see Fig. 2b), much larger than the thickness δ of the atomic sheets. Typically, distances of the order of $L - \delta \approx 20 \text{ \AA}$ between two adjacent atomic layers are chosen. The integration over the corresponding flat and, hence, 2D BZ (Fig. 2c) is replaced by an $N \times N \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh of the Monkhorst-Pack type [50]. Minimum values are $N = 6$ for total energy calculations. Usually meshes are larger with about $N = 12$ or even $N = 24$. Atomic arrangements are typically assumed to be relaxed, when the residual atomic forces are smaller than 1 meV/\AA and the total energy does not vary more than 10^{-5} eV/atom . The stability of a freestanding 2D crystal or such a system deposited on a sub-

strate is investigated by comparing local minima on the total energy surface for a given number of atoms per 2D unit cell (Fig. 2c) or even comparing such extrema of the grand canonical thermodynamic potential with varying chemical potentials of the atomic species [49]. A minimum on the total energy surface is illustrated in Fig. 3 for silicene on top of a H-passivated Si(111) surface with and without vdW interaction [51]. If a given atomic arrangement represents a saddle point on the total energy face, only a metastable or unstable structure can be proven by calculation of the phonon branches $\omega_j(\mathbf{q})$ versus wavevector in the BZ applying the density functional perturbation theory (DFPT) [52] as also implemented in the VASP or QUANTUM ESPRESSO code combined with e.g. the PHONOPY package [53]. Mode softening and imaginary phonon frequencies indicate a violation of the dynamical stability.

2.1.2. Graphene-like structures

Illustrating examples are differently buckled graphene-like structures of Si and Ge, planar (PL) (graphene-like, sp^2 -bonded with a buckling parameter $\Delta = 0$), low-buckled (LB) ($0 < \Delta < a/\sqrt{24}$) and high-buckled (HB) (nearly sp^3 -bonded with $\Delta \gtrsim a/\sqrt{24}$) structures [54]. The energy diagram in Fig. 4 shows that the PL configuration is not stable in comparison to the LB honeycomb structure with an intermediate buckling parameter Δ given in Table 1. HB structures with a much larger buckling have imaginary phonon frequencies of the acoustic branches in a large portion of the BZ. Consequently, among the honeycomb structures only the LB ones are expected to be dynamically stable [17, 54, 55, 56]. This result seems to be also valid for stanene [57, 58]. However, other DFT studies suggest that the HB phase of

tin or lead is more stable than the LB one [59].

Table 1: Structural (lattice constant a , bond length d , buckling Δ) and electronic (Fermi velocity v_F , fundamental band gap E_g , effective carrier mass m^* in units of the free electron mass m , static electronic polarizability α_{2D}) parameters of freestanding LB Xenes from *ab initio* calculations using different approaches for XC.

parameter	graphene	silicene	germanene	stanene	XC treatment	Ref.
a (Å)	2.468	3.868	4.060	4.673 / 4.68	PBE	[17, 57, 60]
		3.83	3.97		LDA	[60, 54]
d (Å)	1.425	2.233, 2.278	2.344, 2.445	2.698 / 2.83	PBE	[17, 57, 60]
		2.25, 2.240	2.38, 2.368		LDA	[60, 54]
Δ (Å)	0.00	0.45, 0.443	0.69, 0.695	0.85 / 0.85	PBE	[17, 57, 60]
		0.44, 0.427	0.64, 0.640		LDA	[60, 54]
v_F (10^6 m/s)	0.83	0.53	0.52	0.48	PBE	[17]
	1.01	0.65	0.62	0.55	HSE	[17]
E_g (meV)	0.0	1.5 / 1.55	24 / 23.9	73	PBE	[17, 61]
	0.0	1.9	33	101	HSE	[17]
m^* (m)	0.000	0.0005	0.0078	0.0279	PBE	[17]
	0.000	0.0004	0.0075	0.0294	HSE	[17]
α_{2D} (Å)	–	76.2	71.4	39.1	PBE	

The lattice parameters in Table 1 exhibit the same tendencies as in the bulk case with the XC potential, LDA for underestimation (overbinding)

and GGA-PBE for overestimation (underbinding) of atomic distances. The chemical trends are unique along the group-IVA as clearly visible for the hexagonal lattice constant a . As in graphene the bond lengths d are slightly smaller than those in sp^3 -hybridized bulk diamond geometries. The vertical distortion of the pristine layer is characterized by the buckling parameter Δ , which shows a similar chemical trend as a and d . Vanishing Δ for graphene is related to the sp^2 bonding. For the other Xenon the optimized Δ remains smaller than the value $\Delta = a/\sqrt{24}$ of complete sp^3 hybridization. The actual values characterize a mixed $sp^2 - sp^3$ bonding.

2.1.3. Polymorphs / allotropes

Within the hexagonal geometries various bucklings exist, besides the above discussed alternating chair-like buckling also boat- and washboard-like structures [56]. In the graphene case the two latter atomic arrangements are unstable. The corresponding starting configurations converge into the flat sp^2 -bonded pristine geometry. For the other Xenon the chair-like geometries are generally more favorable.

The buckling resulting in the chair-like geometry causes the overlap of π and σ orbitals in LB Xenon, but the π bonds are relatively weak. Therefore, by adding additional group-IV atoms, more sp^3 -like hybridizations can be formed. This tendency may result in the formation of relatively stable dumbbell (DB) bonding units. Such a process is exothermic and spontaneous, without overcoming any barriers [62]. The addition of Si adatoms to pristine silicene (see Fig. 5) indeed results in a dumbbell geometry with a lower total energy compared to the LB structure [63, 64, 65]. The extra group-IV atom pushes the atom underneath to form a dumbbell-like struc-

ture with 3+1 coordination [63]. One dumbbell unit in a unit cell gives a trigonal dumbbell (TD) geometry, while two such structural units lead to a hexagonal dumbbell (HD) arrangement. A further increase of the unit cell, which results in a 2×2 translational lattice in the basal plane, defines the large honeycomb dumbbell (LHD) group-IV sheet with still two dumbbell units in one cell [66].

All the dumbbell geometries represent three-layer structures with a flat or slightly buckled hexagonal basal plane (see Fig. 5) but a different density of adatoms. A similar atomic arrangement is given by a MoS_2 -derived atomic geometry but with higher adatom density [65] or a kagome lattice (KL). Its atomic structure follows a recent suggestion for a three-dimensional (3D) elemental carbon polymorph with fourfold-coordinated C atoms and 60° bond angles in triangles [67, 68]. For these 2D carbon allotropes the cohesive energies, obtained as difference of total energy of the 2D structure per atom minus the total energy of a free atom, are listed in Table 2 together with energies for the other group-IV elements [65]. While in the carbon case the flat

Table 2: Cohesive energy (in eV) for 2D allotropes of group-IV materials computed within DFT-PBE [65]. In parenthesis other theoretical values are given [66]. For comparison the energies of the 3D diamond structure are also listed. The energy value in red indicates the most favorable freestanding 2D polymorph.

element	LB	LHD	TD	HD	MoS_2	KL	diamond
C	7.90	6.94	6.96	6.07	5.22	6.59	7.77
Si	3.89 (3.85)	4.10 (4.16)	3.94 (4.01)	3.95 (4.02)	3.90	3.70	4.54
Ge	3.19	3.35	3.22	3.30	3.29	3.09	3.67
Sn	2.68	2.86	2.74	2.84	2.91	2.11	3.12

graphene represents the lowest-energy structure, the dumbbell geometries, especially the LHD one, are energetically favored for freestanding 2D Si and Ge polymorphs. Such a dumbbell arrangement with two dumbbell units in a hexagonal unit cell with ten atoms and the space group D_{6h}^1 ($P6/mmm$) and point group D_{6h} ($6/mmm$) has been also favored in the Sn case [58]. However, Table 2 illustrates that a MoS₂-like geometry further lowers the total energy per Sn atom. Despite the energetics observed for freestanding group-IV sheets, in this review monolayer group-IV systems will be mostly identified with silicene, germanene, and stanene in the chair-like LB geometry. Deviating denotations will be mentioned.

Along the row C→Sn the cohesive energies exhibit a monotonous trend, despite the change in the crystal structure from LB to LHD and to MoS₂. Interestingly the energies along this row are associated hardly with a lowering of symmetry, which may be illustrated by the point group of the full hexagonal or trigonal space groups. The point group D_{6h} for graphene (instead of D_{3d} in the buckled cases) remains for the LHD geometries but becomes D_{3h} for the HD arrangements or even C_{3v} in the TD case (only for C D_{3h} is conserved). However, in the MoS₂ case the central group-IV atom is sixfold coordinated and the two adatoms realize bonds by ‘nematic’ orbitals originating from sp^2 orbitals [69]. The point group is still D_{3h} , which is also conserved in the KL case. Surprisingly, recently a favorable atomically thin tin layer has been proposed to be a metallic double layer with a square lattice, i.e., with a square (translational) symmetry [70].

The trend observed in Table 2 that with rising atomic number the LB phase becomes unstable is confirmed by theoretical studies on buckling of

monolayer tin and lead [59]. The lowest-energy polymorph of these two materials is the HB one with a metallic electronic ground state. Other calculations [71, 72] predict a buckled honeycomb geometry for plumbene with $a = 4.93 \text{ \AA}$, $d = 3.00 (2.99) \text{ \AA}$, and $\Delta = 0.94 (0.93) \text{ \AA}$ with a gap of $E_g = 200$ or $400 (421) \text{ meV}$. Also the topological character of plumbene is under debate.

2.2. Functionalized layers

2.2.1. SiC

The intrinsic semimetallicity (perhaps better in the undoped case: zero-gap multivalley semiconductor character) of graphene and graphene-like group-IV sheets largely limits their application in functional devices. One possible solution to overcome the limitation seems to be 2D alloys of the group-IV elements [73, 74]. In three dimensions one knows that only equally mixed Si and C atoms form a stable crystal, SiC, which exhibits a pronounced polytypism with about 240 cubic, hexagonal and rhombohedral polytypes [75] (and references therein). This is also valid in two dimensions [73, 74]. Experimental evidence is due to the discovered stability of SiC nanotubes [76].

Indeed, total energy calculations show the stability of SiC sheets [77]. The fact that each second atom is carbon with a tendency for sp^2 bonding results in an unbuckled, flat graphene-like geometry, called silicographene [78]. The length of its Si-C bonds $d = 1.79 \text{ \AA}$ is intermediate between the C-C bond length in graphene and the Si-Si distance in silicene (see Table 1). It is somewhat smaller than the Si-C distances of about $d = 1.9 \text{ \AA}$ in bulk SiC polytypes [75]. An important hint for the stability of freestanding SiC sheets is given by the excess energy, $E_{\text{exc}} = E_{\text{tot}}(\text{silicene}) + E_{\text{tot}}(\text{graphene}) - E_{\text{tot}}(\text{SiC})$

silicongraphene) = -0.02 eV / cell. There is no gain in forming a freestanding pristine SiC sheet with respect to graphene and silicene.

2.2.2. Halogenated and hydrogenated Xenes

A promising route to tune the electronic properties of graphene is via chemical functionalizations [22, 79]. The binding of radical groups such as fluorine, hydroxyl, epoxide, or hydrogen to graphene forms mixed covalent-ionic bonds and transforms the trigonal sp^2 in-plane bonding to tetragonal sp^3 atomic arrangements. The radicals are adsorbed with a significant randomness, such as randomly adsorbed epoxide and hydroxyl sidegroups forming GO [80, 81]. The nomenclature of fully ordered and alternately fluorinated and hydrogenated graphene in chair configuration is fluorographene [79, 82] and graphane [81, 83], respectively.

Corresponding fluorinated silicene, germanene, and stanene have been systematically studied within the DFT-LDA framework [84]. They are found to be energetically stable and, therefore, proposed to be easily synthesized in the laboratory. More interesting is the property of halogenated germanene sheets (GeX with $X = \text{F, Cl, Br, or I}$) [85, 86] or functionalized stanene ones (SnX) [57] to be a 2D TI. Hydrogenated and halogenated plumbene monolayers have been also characterized within the DFT framework [72]. A schematic representation of the resulting bonding geometry is displayed in Fig. 6. Hydrogenated and halogenated monolayers have been intensively investigated within DFT-PBE. Resulting structural parameters are listed in Table 3. As examples the Ge-derived 2D systems are chosen. While GeX sheets are 2D TIs independent of the adatom $X = \text{F, Cl, Br, or I}$, only GeI layers using the HSE approach to the electronic structure but DFT-

Table 3: Structural and electronic parameters of pure, halogenated and hydrogenated germanene (chosen as group-IV example) in chair-like geometry from DFT-PBE and generalized DFT-HSE calculations. Besides the hexagonal lattice constant a , the buckling Δ of the basal plane, the bond length $d_{\text{Ge-X}}$ to the adsorbed atoms X, and the indirect (first value) or direct (second value) gap E_g at Γ , also the topological invariant Z_2 is given.

parameter	Ge	GeI	GeBr	GeCl	GeF	GeH	XC	Ref.
a (\AA)	4.06	4.31	4.25	4.23	4.22	4.09	PBE	[87, 88]
	4.06	4.32	4.25	4.24	4.30	4.09	PBE	[86]
	4.06	4.32	4.25	4.24	4.13		PBE	[85]
Δ (\AA)	0.69	0.69			0.58	0.73	PBE	[87, 88]
	0.69	0.68	0.69	0.67	0.62		PBE	[85]
		0.69					PBE	[86]
$d_{\text{Ge-X}}$ (\AA)	–	2.57	2.35	2.19	1.79	1.56	PBE	[85]
		2.57					PBE	[86]
E_g (meV)	24	312	162	99	109	870 /1080	PBE	[87, 88]
	33	296	62	370	168/560	1520 /1820	HSE	[87, 88]
		300/540	180/270	130/210	130/210	130/200	PBE	[86]
	24	162	237	86			PBE	[85]
Z_2	1	1	0	0	0	0	HSE	[87, 88]
	1	1	1	1	1	0	PBE	[86]

PBE geometries are found to show the QSH phase. In the case of the other halogenated monolayers the topological character also depends on the actual gap value and, hence, on the applied XC functional. GeF, GeCl, and GeBr may be trivial insulators but can be driven into nontrivial topological phases with sizeable gaps under tensile strain [86].

In the hydrogenated cases – silicane, germanane, and stanane – the atomic

geometry qualitatively agrees with that displayed in Fig. 6. Significant gaps are opened at the zone center of the BZ, so that not only SiH but also GeH and SnH are trivial insulators [57, 86]. In the case of silicane and germanane, total energy calculations found that the chair-like and boat-like configurations are the most stable buckled ones with nearly equal energies [89]. Other *ab-initio* studies [23, 90] clearly favor the chair-like configuration similar to the findings for graphane [83]. Lattice and electronic structure parameters are listed in Table 4. The dynamical stability of silicane and germanane

Table 4: Structural (lattice constant a , bond length d_{IV-IV} and d_{IV-H} , buckling Δ) and electronic (fundamental gap E_g , electron affinity A , ionization energy I , electron mass at Γ m^* , reduced interband mass at Γ μ^* , static electronic polarizability α_{2D}) parameters of chair-like graphane, silicane, germanane, and stanane from DFT total energy and electronic structure calculations [91]. The structural parameters of stanane go back to Ref. [84]. Gap values from Ref. [23] concern the boat-like crystal structure, while the others, e.g. from Refs. [89, 92], are computed for the chair-like geometry. Similar values have been also calculated for graphane, silicane and germanane using LDA and GW [94].

parameter	graphane	silicane	germanane	stanane	XC	Reference
a (Å)	2.54	3.89	4.02		GGA	[91]
	2.514	3.820	4.091	4.719/4.567	LDA	[23, 93]
d_{IV-IV} (Å)	1.540	2.36	2.39		GGA	[91]
	1.520	2.319	2.338	2.846/2.764	LDA	[23, 93]
d_{IV-H} (Å)	1.11	1.50	1.56		GGA	[91]
	1.084	1.502	1.530	1.738/1.722	LDA	[23, 93]
Δ (Å)	0.46	0.72	0.73		GGA	[91]
	0.45	0.72	0.65	0.82/0.83	LDA	[23, 93]
E_g (eV)	5.4	3.6	2.4		GW on GGA	[91]
	5.4	3.8	3.5	1.63	GW on GGA/LDA	[89, 92, 93, 95]
	3.5/3.5	2.36/2.0	1.34/1.5	0.57	GGA/LDA	[23, 91, 93]
A (eV)	0.3	2.5	3.3		GW on GGA	[91]
I (eV)	5.7	6.1	5.7		GW on GGA	[91]
m^* (m)	1.04	0.16	0.08		GGA	[91]
μ^* (m)	0.28	0.09	0.05		GGA	[91]
α_{2D} (Å)	1.1	3.1	3.5		GGA	[91]

has been proven using phonon calculations [96, 97]. A stable hydrogenated

form should also exist for silicongraphene, silicongraphane [78]. In contrast to silicene, germanene, stanene, silicane, and stanane, as theoretically stable species, only germanane, GeH, has been really experimentally prepared, for instance by deintercalation of CaGe_2 [98, 99]. In addition to the freestanding graphane-like sheets of hydrogenated germanene, recently, also another Ge-derived 2D system, a methyl-substituted germanane GeCH_3 , has been synthesized [100]. The preparation of other chemically modified silicene and germanene analogues were also reported [101]. Very recently it has been proven that the deintercalation technique, here applied on CaSi_2 , produces Si-derived nanosheets, which consist of buckled Si monolayers with a primarily monohydride termination [102]. Measurements show an optical band gap of about 2.5 eV with a direct-like behavior.

2.3. Epitaxial group-IV sheets on metallic substrates

2.3.1. Silicene on Ag(111)

The majority of growth experiments on 2D Si layers has been performed using a substrate mostly being metallic in character. A prototypical substrate is silver with its Ag(111) surface. The use of the Ag substrate was driven by the general assumption of complete immiscibility between silicon and silver [103]. Another driving force was the observation of highly dense silicene nanoribbons on the Ag(110) surface [104]. Due to its highly symmetric hexagonal surface unit cell, the Ag(111) surface appears as the natural option to extend silicene nanoribbons to a sheet-like 2D overlayer. The synthesis of silicene has been performed in the ultra-high vacuum (UHV) by evaporating Si from a Si source while keeping the Ag sample at a certain temperature, for instance in the range between 520–560 K [105]. Similar

preparation techniques based basically on a molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) have been published by other research groups applying substrate temperatures of 400–670 K [69, 106, 107, 108].

As a typical result images of such Si overlayers are displayed in Fig. 7. They are obtained by scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) [49]. Such high-resolution STM topographies, sometimes supported by low electron energy diffraction (LEED) patterns, are interpreted by a coincidence lattice method [49, 110] and denoted applying the Wood notation [49, 111]. A unit cell $(\sqrt{n} \times \sqrt{m})R\phi^\circ$ with integer n , m , and \sqrt{nm} contains \sqrt{nm} 1×1 primitive unit cells of the original Bravais lattice. Here a multiple of the graphene-like hexagonal cell of silicene, rotated by an angle ϕ , thereby may be slightly strained, appears on top of a nonprimitive $(\sqrt{n'} \times \sqrt{m'})R\phi'^\circ$ unit cell of the Ag(111) surface. Commonly, the rotation angles ϕ and ϕ' are not explicitly given in the denotations. The topograph in Fig. 7a is interpreted as a 3×3 silicene superstructure on top of the Ag(111) 4×4 surface [105]. The atomic geometry has been identified as a honeycomb-like Si lattice on the Ag(111) substrate.

Varying the substrate temperature and controlling the Si deposition flux various other Si/Ag(111) combinations are achieved. Four different silicene overlayer phases are indicated by other Ag(111) supercells in Fig. 7b [109]. Besides the 4×4 also $\sqrt{13} \times \sqrt{13}$, $2\sqrt{3} \times 2\sqrt{3}$ and $\sqrt{7} \times \sqrt{7}$, more strictly $(\sqrt{13} \times \sqrt{13})R13.9^\circ$, $(2\sqrt{3} \times 2\sqrt{3})R30^\circ$, and $(\sqrt{7} \times \sqrt{7})R19.1^\circ$, phases are found [112]. Corresponding Si overlayers could be besides 3×3 also $(\sqrt{7} \times \sqrt{7})R19.1^\circ$, and 2×2 . Also a $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ translational symmetry is discussed, mainly for silicene multilayers [113]. Epitaxial silicene self-organizes in dif-

ferent superstructures, i.e., different atomic arrangements, depending on the lattice mismatch with the host substrate and the substrate temperature. Thereby, the layer buckling and stoichiometry act as additional degrees of freedom. The appearance of different atomic geometries of the ‘silicene’ overlayer may be referred to as its polymorphic nature, namely the capability of the Si atoms to accommodate on a nearly commensurate substrate in buckled structures with overall hexagonal symmetry and mutually different lattice periodicities [114].

STM and LEED give information about the lateral lattice parameters. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) is able to complete the structural characterization by the atomic buckling and, hence the sublattice separation. For silicene on Ag(111) the low-temperature AFM gives buckling amplitudes in the range of $0.8 - 1.1 \text{ \AA}$ with 0.1 \AA precision [115] in good agreement with DFT calculations for 3×3 silicene on Ag(111) 4×4 of $\Delta = 0.78 \text{ \AA}$ [111, 116]. The buckling itself depends on the lateral atomic distances and, therefore, can be slightly modified by strain. Compressive biaxial strain increases the buckling with rising strength. Tensile biaxial strain, however, tends to converge the buckling against a constant value slightly below the strainfree value in Table 1, at least in the case of silicene [117, 118].

The experimental information from STM and AFM images, LEED patterns, and electronic structure studies can be used to construct atomic structure models for the Si overlayers, for which, in addition, their stability and relaxed geometry may be proven by total energy investigations using DFT. Atomic models for four phases of silicene on top of Ag(111) are displayed in Fig. 8a together with calculated filled-state STM images (Fig. 8b) and adsor-

bate energy versus Si chemical potential μ_{Si} curves (Fig. 8c) [112]. The actual value of the chemical potential simulates the preparation conditions including substrate temperature. Interestingly, all the studied phases, which describe different Si coverages of the Ag(111) surface and different biaxial strains as a consequence of the assumed coincidence lattices, are stable under certain preparation conditions expressed by μ_{Si} . They represent Si/Ag(111) systems with hexagonal or trigonal symmetry. All the underlying non-primitive 2D Bravais lattices are hexagonal, so that the 2D electronic structure of the overlayer systems, the silicene polymorphs, has to be discussed in a hexagonal BZ [112].

The total energy studies clearly indicate a strong bonding of Si atoms at the Si/Ag(111) interface. This fact is in agreement with the strong silicon reactivity found experimentally at the Ag(111) surface [119]. Nevertheless, such a silicene overlayer can be exfoliated from a synthesized layered 3×3 silicene/ 4×4 Ag(111)/mica heterosystem. The system is first capped by an Al_2O_3 layer. In a subsequent step an *ex situ* delamination of the silver/silicene/alumina sandwich combined with an upside-down transfer onto the device substrate, SiO_2 on a highly doped Si wafer, happens. Finally, a silicene channel and the source/drain electrodes, defined in the native silver film, are patterned [120]. In the fabricated field-effect transistor (FET) the silicene layer is measured to have a room-temperature mobility of about $100 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ attributed to acoustic-phonon-limited transport [121] applying corroborating theoretical predictions for lattice vibrations [122]. Most important, however, is the fact that the transfer characteristics measured for several prepared FETs provides device evidence of silicene's Dirac-like band

structure, especially by finding a Dirac peak in the function of resistance versus gate overdrive voltage [120].

2.3.2. Other Xene/metal combinations

An appropriate substrate for an epitaxial deposition of silicene or germanene should fulfill conditions such as: (i) Its surface atoms should be immiscible with the overlayer ones. A metal used as substrate should not form a silicide or germanide with silicon and germanium, respectively. (ii) The silicene/germanene lattice and the substrate surface lattice should be nearly commensurable. Nevertheless, a small biaxial strain of the overlayer is allowed. (iii) The chemical interaction with the substrate should be weak, so that in the Xene neither symmetry breaking nor opening of a large gap occurs due to the formation of mixed covalent-ionic interface bonds. A restriction to a vdW interaction seems to be aimed at [51].

Another possibility to grow epitaxially Xenos is the segregation of substrate atoms through a metallic overlayer. STM images of a thin Au(111) film deposited on a Si(111)6×6-Au surface combined with DFT calculations of a two-layer Si/Au system are interpreted to clearly display an atomically resolved planar silicene honeycomb lattice after sample annealing up to 560 K [123]. The seeming almost perfectly flat geometry shares the atomic structure with graphene rather than with LB silicene. The prepared Si overlayer is therefore interpreted as the first experimental evidence of epitaxial planar silicene. More advanced studies may, however, lead to an interpretation including buckling of the overlayer

$\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ silicene deposition was also reported on $\text{ZrB}_2(0001)2 \times 2$ and $\text{Ir}(111)\sqrt{7} \times \sqrt{7}$ substrates [124, 125]. ZrB_2 is a conductive ceramic, typically

grown on Si(111) wafers. The Zr-terminated surface shows a 2×2 superstructure due to adatoms segregated from the Si substrate. Buckled silicene with a $\sqrt{3}\times\sqrt{3}$ reconstruction, which coincides with the 2×2 surface unit cell of ZrB_2 , is formed. The resulting Si-Si bond lengths $2.266 - 2.242 \text{ \AA}$ are rather close to that of freestanding silicene (see Table 1).

Buckled $\sqrt{3}\times\sqrt{3}$ silicene was also obtained on Ir(111) through Si deposition at room temperature and subsequent annealing at 670 K. There are six Si atoms on a Ir(111) $\sqrt{7}\times\sqrt{7}$ surface with seven Ir atoms in a 2D cell. The silicene and Ir surface states are strongly hybridized similarly as in the case of the Ag(111) substrate [126]. A survey of (111) surfaces of fcc metal crystals and (0001) surfaces of hexagonal metals is theoretically evaluated together with metallized Si(111) substrates with respect to a possible growth of nearly unstrained silicene [127].

To avoid the strong bonding between substrate and overlayer, half-metallic highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) was considered as substrate. The inertness of a single graphene layer, its vdW interaction with adjacent layers, and its hexagonal symmetry suggest possible ordered adsorbate structures with no alloy intermixing after deposition of either Si or Ge [128]. Indeed, seemingly islands of silicene may be grown [129]. Also the synthesis of germanene islands is reported [130]. STM measurements show 2D layer islands with a lattice constant $a = 4.2 \pm 0.3 \text{ \AA}$ and a layer buckling of 0.7 \AA , values which closely match the theoretical predictions for freestanding germanene (see Table 1). According to theoretical predictions for freestanding silicene [60], just one normal zone-center vibrational mode is Raman-active, which is the degenerate in-plane E_{2g} phonon with a frequency of 575 cm^{-1} , higher than

the Raman frequency 520 cm^{-1} of diamond-Si. Such a Raman line shifted toward higher frequencies is found in measured spectra and interpreted as indicator for silicene. While recent Raman studies support the formation, at least, of silicene on HOPG [131], the interpretation of the islands on HOPG as almost constrained silicene and germanene has been, however, rejected by other experiments [132]. STM and Raman results can be also interpreted as evidence of intercalation of the silicene nanosheets [133].

The deposition of germanene has been also tried on metal substrates, e.g. the Au(111) surface [134]. A $\sqrt{27} \times \sqrt{27}$ reconstructed germanene coincides with a Au(111) 8×8 surface and germanene armchair edges (for definition see Fig. 9) aligned along the dense Au rows. The projected in-plane Ge-Ge nearest-neighbor distance of 2.56 \AA is, however, found to be larger than that predicted theoretically for the freestanding material (see Table 1). A buckled germanene formation has been observed on Pt(111) substrates [135]. The resulting overlayer system was characterized as a 3×3 germanene on top of a $\sqrt{19} \times \sqrt{19}$ superstructure with respect to the substrate lattice by LEED and STM. More recently, it was suggested that the Ge-induced $\sqrt{19} \times \sqrt{19}$ reconstruction on Pt(111) is a surface alloy composed of Ge_3Pt tetramers which resembles a twisted kagome lattice (see Fig. 5) [136]. Following this idea, Pt has been grown on a Ge(110) substrate and subsequently flash-annealed at high temperature [137]. Formation of 3D metallic Pt-Ge, probably Ge_2Pt , nanocrystals is observed. The outermost layer of the crystallites shows a well-ordered honeycomb lattice, that consists of two hexagonal sublattices, in STM. The nearest-neighbor distance is $2.5 \pm 0.1\text{ \AA}$, while the honeycomb lattice constant is $4.4 \pm 0.2\text{ \AA}$. These values are slightly larger than those of

freestanding germanene in Table 1. The measurement of 2D image potential states on both sides of a germanene layer synthesized on a Ge_2Pt crystal using STM and scanning tunneling spectroscopy (STS) has been interpreted as a clear proof for only a very weak interaction between Ge overlayer and substrate [138].

Germanene seems to be also successfully synthesized on a $\text{Al}(111)$ substrate [139, 140, 141]. First-principles calculations proposed that the overlayer is stabilized by a large buckling, i.e., an upward shift of two Ge atoms in a 3×3 unit cell, of 1.21–1.23 Å [139, 141, 142]. Total-reflection high-energy positron diffraction studies deliver a buckling of 0.94 Å with a spacing of 2.51 Å between the germanene and the $\text{Al}(111)$ substrate [143]. Theoretical studies of germanene on a variety of metallic substrates claim that the Dirac cone of the Ge overlayer is destroyed on the Al, Pt, and Ir substrates but preserved on the Ag and Au substrates, although slightly modified by a minor band hybridization [144].

DFT calculations suggest that a $\text{Ag}(111)$ surface could also be a candidate for growing monolayer stanene [145]. Planar stanene should be stable also on a $\text{Au}(111)1\times 1$ surface [146]. A Sn monolayer deposited on $\text{Au}(111)$ shows similarities but also differences to the expected electronic features of freestanding stanene [147]. For instance, ARPES shows a spin-polarized linearly dispersing band near the BZ center with a rather large Fermi velocity of 1×10^6 m/s. There is one experimental report of highly buckled stanene composed of biatomic layers of $\alpha\text{-Sn}(111)$ grown on Bi_2Te_3 [148]. The epitaxial growth of well-ordered, large area, planar stanene is also possible by Sn deposition onto a $\text{Ag}(111)$ substrate [149]. A nearly perfect planar layer

is formed, growing in a 2D island mode on the initial Ag_2Sn surface alloy. The growth of high-quality stanene on $\text{Cu}(111)$ by low-temperature MBE has been demonstrated [150]. The prepared flakes are close to a 2×2 Sn overlayer structure on a 1×1 substrate. The discovered ultraflat stanene shows an $s-p$ band-inverted gap of about 0.3 eV at the Γ point.

A totally different method has been reported for the large-area epitaxial growth of plumbene [151]. Plumbene is prepared by segregation from $\text{Pd}_{1-x}\text{Pb}_x(111)$ alloys grown on $\text{Pd}(111)$ substrates upon heating/alloying of thin Pb films deposited at room temperature. STM images of the Pb overlayer show a planar honeycomb structure with a lateral lattice constant of 4.8–4.9 Å corresponding to that of the standalone 2D plumbene.

2.3.3. Xenes on insulators

Apart from near lattice matching, the avoidance of strong covalent and ionic bonds between overlayer and substrate could be an important ingredient to prepare silicene, germanene or stanene by a vdW epitaxy [152]. Hydrogen-passivated $\text{Si}(111)1\times 1$ and $\text{Ge}(111)1\times 1$ surfaces (see Fig. 3a) could be an option [51]. These substrates are almost lattice-matched. Another option may be the Cl-passivation of the cleavage $\text{Si}(111)$ surface. After repeated annealing a bulk-like 1×1 surface appears [153]. A stable monolayer of Cl^- ions covers the $\text{Si}(111)1\times 1$ surface with almost Si^+ ions in the topmost substrate layer. A silicene overlayer may be vdW bonded on the passivated substrate as illustrated in Fig. 10a [154]. A similar suggestion is made for the F-terminated $\text{CaF}_2(111)1\times 1$ surface (see Fig. 10b). Monolayer germanene is successfully fabricated on a semiconducting diamond-like germanium film with the support of a $\text{Ag}(111)$ substrate [155]. A linear-

like energy-momentum dispersion relation and reasonable Fermi velocity of $v_F = (3.7 \pm 0.3) \times 10^5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ are derived from the quasiparticle interference patterns in a $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ superstructure. Only a small gap of 78 meV is opened between the Dirac cones.

VdW epitaxy has been considered as a promising approach for the preparation of building blocks at the nanoscale on 2D materials [152, 156]. For instance, a significant enhancement of the nucleation of germanium on graphene has been demonstrated. Indeed, the stability of silicene and germanene but also stanene on graphene has been predicted theoretically [157, 158]. Graphene itself can be epitaxially grown on hexagonal SiC(0001) substrates [159, 160, 161]. This fact not only suggests deposition of Xenes or Xanes on graphene-covered SiC surfaces but also to grow quasifreestanding 2D crystals on a passivated or buffer-layer-covered SiC(0001) substrate. Examples are Xenes on hydrogenated Si- or C-terminated SiC(0001) [162] or stanene on a decorated SiC(0001) surface [163]. Indeed, first-principles supercell calculations demonstrated that the C-terminated SiC(000 $\bar{1}$) surface covered by graphene could be used as a substrate to epitaxially grow Xenes in general with a LB structure [164]. This is schematically illustrated in Fig. 11. Since the interaction between overlayer and substrate is weak, the Dirac cone features in the electronic structure of freestanding Xenes are almost maintained. However, the interaction varies with the group-IV element. In the case of silicene on graphene/SiC its topological character is destroyed, while it is conserved in the case of germanene. Experimentally, attempts to grow 2D silicon on graphene deposited on 6H-SiC(0001) were not successful, despite the variation of the substrate temperature in a wide range [165]. In addition

to the passivation by a graphene overlayer [164], also the growth of stanene or fluorostanene on H- or F-passivated SiC(0001) substrates has been suggested [166]. The *ab initio* calculations predict the survival of the topological character of stanene on H-passivated surfaces and of fluorostanene on H- and F-passivated ones.

Studying the graphene/SiC system, instead of silicene, germanene or stanene growth on top, the possibility of intercalating Si/Ge/Sn under the graphene layer could be another option. This was proposed studying this effect for Si with the graphene/Ru substrate system [167]. In a certain way the intercalation idea has been also applied to CaSi₂ crystals, which can be regarded as a silicon analog of graphite intercalation compounds, where an ordered Si atom layer is sandwiched by calcium sheets [168]. Indeed, the observation of Dirac cones in the intercalated compound CaSi₂ has been published [169]. The robust Dirac dispersion has been confirmed theoretically [170]. This idea to prepare group-IV monolayers has been also corroborated in the case of Ca-intercalated multilayer germanene [171], where CaGe₂ is the starting point for the preparation of germanane [98]. The preparation of bilayer silicene structures seems to be possible also via intercalation of F ions into CaSi₂ [172].

Besides graphene also other 2D layers have been studied as substrates for growth of Xenes. Examples are silicene and germanene on MoS₂ [173, 174, 175]. The compressively strained germanene overlayer still has a much larger lattice constant $a = 3.8 \pm 0.2 \text{ \AA}$ than MoS₂, slightly underestimating the predictions for freestanding material (see Table 1). Recently the optical conductivity of ultrathin Si nanosheets grown on Al₂O₃(0001) has been re-

ported [176]. Because of its huge band gap of the substrate of 8.8 eV [177], the Dirac points of a silicene-like overlayer should be in the middle of this gap [178]. Indeed, first-principles calculations including the excitation aspect clearly show that silicene-derived linear bands appear near the Fermi level. In these studies the substrate is simulated by a Al_2O_3 layer in the kagome lattice geometry with a gap close to that of the bulk material [179]. An illustration of the atomic structure of this bilayer system is depicted in Fig. 12. Similar theoretical predictions have been made within the DFT framework for silicene, germanene or stanene combined with a hBN layer [180]. There are also experimental attempts to grow thin Sn films or even stanene in MBE-like experiments on nonmetallic substrates such as InSb(111) [181, 182] or Bi_2Te_3 [148].

2.4. Multilayers

Experiments show that multilayer silicene on Ag(111) can grow up to 50 atomic layers with a unique $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ reconstruction [183, 184]. Indeed, $(\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3})\text{R}30^\circ$ reconstructed epitaxial multilayer islands seem to grow on top of the first 3×3 reconstructed silicene wetting layer on Ag(111) substrates. The multilayer structure is not very clear. STM studies suggest a variation of the atomic geometry from layer to layer. Angular-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES) seems to indicate Dirac cones with a Fermi velocity of $v_F = 0.3 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ [183] and a Dirac point position 0.33 eV below the Fermi level [185]. Few-layer epitaxial systems have been also reported for germanene but on a clean Au(111) surface [134].

The atomic geometry of each silicene-like layer as well as the atomic arrangement in the observed Si islands on Ag(111) are under debate. This

concerns the translational symmetry, the atomic arrangement as well as the stacking of the layers. There is also the question about the relation of the symmetry of the STM images to the true atomic geometry. First-principles studies of bilayer silicene [186, 187] give different answers in explaining the $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ structure observed experimentally. Moreover, no Moiré pattern of two twisted silicene layers as occurs for graphene (see Fig. 13) has been reported. Theoretical studies of multilayer silicene, prepared by bottom-up epitaxy on Ag(111) and presumably vdW bonded, show tendencies for rearrangements toward the diamond structure of bulk silicon [188, 189]. With increasing number of atomic layers reconstruction elements of the Si(111) surface, such as 2×1 π -bonded chains and 7×7 dimer-adatom-stacking fault structures (see [49]) are found [188], or even spontaneous transformations into the sp^3 -bonded Si phase [189]. Interestingly, because of the unique LB structure of monolayer silicene, a robust electronic kagome lattice (see Fig. 5) has been successfully induced by Moiré patterns after twisting silicene multilayers [190]. The experimental realization has been demonstrated by means of STM/STS with the emergence of a flat band in the electronic structure.

3. Electronic states

3.1. Xenes

3.1.1. Basics

The DFT total energy studies of the atomic structure also immediately deliver the electronic eigenvalues $\varepsilon_\nu(\mathbf{k})$ and the corresponding Bloch-Pauli spinors $|\nu\mathbf{k}\rangle$ for each Bloch state characterized by the band index ν and the

(2D) wave vector $\mathbf{k} \in \text{BZ}$ as the solutions of the Kohn-Sham (KS) equation [36] of the DFT with a given XC potential. For LB silicene the KS Bloch bands obtained with the PBE XC functional [44] are displayed versus the hexagonal BZ in Fig. 14. The presence of layer buckling suggests a mixture of sp^3 and sp^2 hybridization (see Sec. 2.1.2). It is due to the larger atom-atom distance-induced weakening of the π -bonding. Nevertheless, around the Fermi level silicene shows similar π and π^* bands as graphene. A vanishing gap (without SOC) near the K and K' points at the BZ boundary and the formation of slightly asymmetric Dirac cones are visible near these high-symmetry points. Far away from the Dirac points the bands possess a stronger σ and σ^* character as in bulk diamond silicon. However, the bands are still affected by the 2D hexagonal geometry. As a consequence band crossing features appear e.g. about 9 eV below the Fermi level with touching points at the same K and K' points. Also in the higher conduction bands the consequences of the hexagonal symmetry are visible.

The KS band structures are computed for the ground state of the electronic systems. The excitation aspect, which is needed to describe correctly the energies measured in ARPES, inverse photoemission spectroscopy (IPES), and scanning tunneling spectroscopy (STS), is not taken into account. Consequently, energy gaps, interband energies, and electron ionization energies are systematically underestimated in the KS approach with a local or semilocal XC potential [193]. To overcome this limitation, the XC effects on the single-particle excitation or quasiparticle (QP) energies are described by the corresponding self-energy Σ of the many-body perturbation theory (MBPT), typically within Hedin's GW approximation [194, 195] with G as

the single-particle Green function and W as the dynamically screened potential. In practice, Σ is computed in an iterative procedure $G_n W_m$ with the starting point $G_0 W_0$ (the so-called single-shot) calculated from KS eigenvalues and eigenstates. The GW approximation is implemented in codes, for example VASP (see [196]), Yambo [197] or in the CHISIG code [198], based on KS results, in the latter implementation on output of QUANTUM ESPRESSO [37]. Typically the \mathbf{k} -point densities chosen for computing Σ are higher compared to the total energy calculations. The modelling of the 2D systems within the supercell approach (see Sec. 2.1.1) is affected by an artificial long-range Coulomb interaction between two sheets in a distance of L . This can be removed by the use of a truncated Coulomb potential [199, 200] or by using large enough values of L [201]. For illustration the empty and filled bands of graphene in $G_0 W_0$ and DFT-PBE quality are displayed in Fig. 15a. It clearly demonstrates the increase of energy distances between conduction and valence bands as well as the increase of the Fermi velocity from $v_F = 0.78 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ to $1.02 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ or even $1.12 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ by many-body effects [201, 202] in agreement with experimental findings [12] and other $G_0 W_0$ computations [203, 204].

The $G_0 W_0$, but especially iterative GW, calculations are rather time- and memory-consuming. For that reason also other XC treatments by spatially nonlocal hybrid XC functionals, for instance the HSE03/06 one [205, 206], are applied. The combination of some screened short-range exchange effects with local or semilocal XC potentials of the DFT in a generalized KS (gKS) scheme also significantly opens the gaps [196, 207]. As an example the HSE and DFT-GGA band structures of germanene are displayed in Fig. 15b. An

alternative scheme to simulate QP effects is the DFT-1/2 method [208, 209], which can be also applied to 2D crystals [210, 211].

3.1.2. Band gap and dispersion

Band structures in HSE quality are presented in Fig. 16 for freestanding LB graphene, silicene, germanene, and stanene [17]. Without SOC, independent of the group-IV material and the buckling, they exhibit linear bands $\varepsilon_\nu(\mathbf{k}) = \pm\hbar v_F |\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}_{K/K'}|$ crossing at the Dirac points located at K and K' high-symmetry points. They result in Dirac cones with the Fermi velocity v_F , which monotonously decreases from graphene to stanene (see Table 1). Carriers in these bands behave as massless Dirac fermions. Around high-symmetry points at the BZ boundary practically the band structure of graphene is resembled also for silicene, germanene, and stanene, despite the layer buckling. However, far away from K or K' the band dispersion strongly varies with the group-IV element. Going from stanene along germanene and silicene to graphene a significantly $\sigma - \sigma^*$ gap is opened at the Γ point. The characteristic direct gap values at Γ are approximately 1.0, 1.6, 4.0, and more than 7.0 eV (not shown for graphene).

The treatment of the electron spins in the noncollinear approximation and the inclusion of relativistic effects including the SOC in the framework of the Pauli equation mainly modify the bands in Fig. 16 near high-symmetry and crossing points. Not only the fourfold degeneracy of the uppermost valence bands but also the fourfold degeneracy at the Dirac points is lifted. SOC-induced gaps E_g appear at K (or K'). In the low-energy region around the Dirac point the twofold spin-degenerate conduction (valence) band $\nu = +$

($\nu = -$) is described by a dispersion relation of massive Dirac particles [212]

$$\varepsilon_{\pm}(\mathbf{k}) = \pm \sqrt{(E_g/2)^2 + \hbar^2 v_F^2 (\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}_K)^2}. \quad (1)$$

The strongly varying SOC-induced gap values E_g and the Fermi velocities v_F are listed in Table 1 together with the resulting effective carrier masses

$$m^* = \frac{E_g}{2v_F^2}. \quad (2)$$

They follow clear chemical trends. Thereby, the spin-orbit effects are larger using the HSE06 XC functional than using the PBE one, as a consequence of the more localized QP states. Our findings are in good agreement with other recent DFT calculations with E_g values of 1.55 meV (Si), 23.9 meV (Ge), and 73.5 meV (Sn) [61, 212]. For silicene also the v_F values agree well with 0.575 (DFT) and 0.61×10^6 m/s (GW) in other computations [179].

3.1.3. Four-band model

In general, with the single-particle potential $V(\mathbf{x})$ in the Pauli equation the SOC contribution to the Hamiltonian reads in *cgs* units as [193]

$$H_{SO} = \frac{\hbar}{4(mc)^2} [\text{grad}V(\mathbf{x}) \times \mathbf{p}] \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (3)$$

with the momentum operator \mathbf{p} and the vector $\hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ of the Pauli spin matrices. A tight-binding representation with atom-like wave functions of the matrix elements of H_{SO} (3) allows for deeper insights. In the unbuckled honeycomb case, graphene, with two coplanar sublattices, the nearest-neighbor matrix element of (3) is zero, because of the mirror symmetry with respect to an arbitrary bond [212]. Only a tiny SOC-induced gap < 0.05 meV occurs due to the second-order SOC [213]. For the buckled geometries – silicene,

germanene, and stanene – the nearest-neighbor SOC is zero, while the next-nearest-neighbor SOC is nonzero. It can be divided into two parts, those parallel and perpendicular to the basal plane, which may be identified as intrinsic Kane-Mele SOC [214, 215] and intrinsic Rashba SOC [216].

This knowledge about SOC is frequently combined with a second-nearest-neighbor tight-binding (TB) Hamiltonian [212]. Subsequent Fourier transformation leads to an effective low-energy 4×4 $\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ Hamiltonian around a Dirac point K ($\zeta = +$) or K' ($\zeta = -$) with wavevector deviations $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}_{K\zeta}$ and the valley index ζ . In the four-orbital spinor basis $\{|A\rangle, |B\rangle\} \otimes \{|\uparrow\rangle, |\downarrow\rangle\}$ with $|A\rangle$ ($|B\rangle$) as the p_z -orbital at a group-IV atom in the sublattice A (B) (see Fig. 2c) and $|\uparrow\rangle$ ($|\downarrow\rangle$) as the spinor for the spin up (spin down) one finds for the valley $\zeta = +, -$ [212, 217, 218, 219]

$$\hat{H}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = \zeta \begin{pmatrix} \hat{h}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) & \hbar v_F \kappa_{+\zeta} \hat{\sigma}_0 \\ \hbar v_F \kappa_{-\zeta} \hat{\sigma}_0 & -\hat{h}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = (\kappa_x, \kappa_y)$, $\kappa_{\pm\zeta} = \zeta \kappa_x \pm i \kappa_y$, and the 2×2 matrix $\hat{h}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = -\lambda_{SO} \hat{\sigma}_z - a \lambda_R (\kappa_y \hat{\sigma}_x - \kappa_x \hat{\sigma}_y) + U \hat{\sigma}_0$. The matrices $\hat{\sigma}_\alpha$ are the unit ($\alpha = 0$) and Pauli ($\alpha = x, y, z$) 2×2 matrices. The arrangement of the 2×2 sub-Hamiltonians in (4) characterizes in total three intrinsic degrees of freedom: sublattice pseudospin, spin and valley. The different dependences in Hamiltonians (4) illustrate that the Xenes are suitable materials for topological spin- and valleytronics. The Hamiltonians (4) of the two valleys $\zeta = +, -$ are related to each other by the time-reversal symmetry operation. The two parameters λ_{SO} and λ_R characterize the effective SOC acting in-plane and the Rashba effect, respectively. In addition, the action of a vertical electric field F_z due to a vertical bias voltage $U = eF_z \Delta/2$ appears and is illustrated in Fig. 17a.

Practically, $2U$ represents the maximum variation of the staggered sublattice potential between the A and B sites [217, 218]. In an electric device with a gate or, in general, in a tunnel junction with an applied bias voltage as in a STM/STS measurement geometry, such an electric field with strength F_z is always present. However, in the latter case there may be a second field contribution due to different work functions of the Xene layer and the tip material [220].

The lattice parameter a but also the buckling Δ occur in (4). All the parameters of the valley Hamiltonian (4) including the SOC constants and the Fermi velocities are listed in Table 5. The λ_{SO} values for Si, Ge and Sn from [212], however, significantly deviate from the gap values $E_g = 2\lambda_{SO}$ in Table 1. This is due to the relation of the SOC parameters to TB overlap integrals, which are fitted to *ab initio* band structures. For plumbene the parameters increase further, e.g., to about $\lambda_{SO} = 200$ meV, $a = 4.93$ Å, and $\Delta = 0.93$ Å [221, 222]. Other fitting results from first-principles calculations for standalone Si, Ge, Sn and Pb sheets [223] are somewhat different, in particular for Si and Sn with different λ_R/λ_{SO} ratios.

Table 5: Characteristic parameters of low-energy Dirac Hamiltonian (4) derived by fitting a TB model to DFT results [212].

system	a (Å)	Δ (Å)	λ_{SO} (meV)	λ_R (meV)	v_F (10^5 m/s)
graphene	2.46	0	0	0	9.80
silicene	3.86	0.45	3.9	0.7	5.52
germanene	4.02	0.66	46.3	10.7	4.57
stanene	4.70	0.80	64.4	9.5	4.85

Direct diagonalization of the Hamiltonians (4) gives as eigenvalues the four bands near a Dirac point with the valley index $\zeta = +, -$ [87, 212, 224, 225]

$$\varepsilon_{\zeta\nu s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = \nu \left[\hbar^2 v_F^2 \kappa^2 + \left(|U| - \zeta s \sqrt{\lambda_{SO}^2 + a^2 \lambda_R^2 \kappa^2} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\nu = +, -$ indicates the conduction ($\nu = +$) and valence ($\nu = -$) bands and $s = +, -$ the spin orientation. The product ζs indicates the valley-spin coupling leading to opposite spins of the bands at K and K'. Without external field the spin degrees of freedom in the band structure are still degenerate, as a consequence of both TR and inversion symmetry. With external field, however, the spin polarization in each band at K or K' is obvious. At a Dirac point $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = 0$ the bands (5) define a field-dependent gap $E_g(U)$ as well as field-induced band splittings $\Delta\varepsilon(U)$

$$\begin{aligned} E_g(U) &= 2 |\lambda_{SO} - |U||, \\ \Delta\varepsilon(U) &= 2 [|U|\Theta(\lambda_{SO} - |U|) + \lambda_{SO}\Theta(|U| - \lambda_{SO})] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with $\Theta(\varepsilon)$ as the Heaviside step function. The field-modified gap (6) and its linear variation with the bias are displayed in Fig. 17b for germanene [226]. It decreases from $E_g(0) = 2\lambda_{SO}$ to zero at a critical field strength F_z^{crit} with $|U| = \lambda_{SO}$. Typical values are $F_z^{\text{crit}} = 0.2 (3.3, 9.2) \times 10^6$ V/cm for silicene (germanene, stanene) [226], estimated with DFT values Δ and HSE gaps E_g from Table 1, in rough agreement with other DFT calculations [87, 227]. The larger, TB-derived SOC parameters in Table 5 give, however, rise to larger critical field strengths. The critical field strength, e.g. in Fig. 17b, also characterizes the transition from a topological or quantum

spin Hall (QSH) insulator in a trivial or band insulator [61, 217, 226]. The topology tunable by an external field affords an electronic switch, where the logic state is dictated by the topological phase transition rather than by the charge depletion/inversion as in conventional semiconductors [228]. The electric field influence on the gap (6) also shines light on the vanishing gap of germanene synthesized on different substrates measured by STS [220]. The electric field due to the difference in the work function of germanene of about 3.8 eV to that of the tip material [138] may compensate the SOC-induced gap opening.

The band structure in general remains less influenced by an external electric field as shown in Fig. 18 [87]. However, in the presence of such a field the inversion symmetry is broken and the point group changes from D_{3d} to C_{3v} . Twofold spin-degenerate bands split. This is illustrated for the K and K' points in the insets of Fig. 18 and by the band splitting $\Delta\varepsilon(U)$ (6). According to (6) the splitting increases linearly from $F_z = 0$ to $F_z = F_z^{\text{crit}}$, while a constant splitting $2\lambda_{SO}$ appears for the conduction and the valence bands increasing further the field strength to $F_z > F_z^{\text{crit}}$.

The inversion of $\hat{G}_\zeta^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \hbar z) = \hat{H}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) - \hbar z \hat{1}$ gives the 4×4 Green function matrix $\hat{G}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \hbar z)$, which belongs to a valley Hamiltonian (4). Its spectral behavior is given by a matrix of spectral functions according to $\hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon) = i \lim_{\eta \rightarrow +0} \left\{ \hat{G}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon + i\eta) - \hat{G}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon - i\eta) \right\}$. In some special cases the latter ones can be easily derived. For instance, in the limit of vanishing Rashba

SOC $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ (justified by Table 5) one finds with $\lambda_{\pm} = \lambda_{SO} \pm |U|$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A}_{\zeta}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon) = & \\ & \zeta \pi \sum_{\nu=+,-} \sum_{s=+,-} \left\{ \frac{\delta_{(\zeta s)-1}}{\varepsilon_{-\nu+}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})} \delta(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{-\nu+}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})) \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_+ + \zeta\varepsilon & 0 & \hbar v_F \kappa_{+\zeta} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \hbar v_F \kappa_{-\zeta} & 0 & -\lambda_+ + \zeta\varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{\delta_{(\zeta s)1}}{\varepsilon_{-\nu-}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})} \delta(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{-\nu-}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})) \begin{pmatrix} -\lambda_- + \zeta\varepsilon & 0 & \hbar v_F \kappa_{+\zeta} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \hbar v_F \kappa_{-\zeta} & 0 & \lambda_- + \zeta\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right\}. \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Here the Dirac delta function $\delta(\varepsilon)$ and the Kronecker symbol δ_{ij} ($i, j = \pm 1$) have been introduced.

The spectral function matrix (7) is normalized $\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d\varepsilon}{2\pi} \hat{A}_{\zeta}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon) = \hat{1}$. It gives rise to a total DOS (per energy and area) from both valleys at K and K' [225]

$$\begin{aligned} N(\varepsilon) &= \sum_{\zeta=+,-} \int \frac{d^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}}{(2\pi)^2} \text{Tr} \left\{ \hat{A}_{\zeta}(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon) \right\} \\ &= \sum_{\zeta=+,-} \sum_{\nu=+,-} \sum_{s=+,-} \int \frac{d^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}}{(2\pi)^2} \delta(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{\zeta \nu s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})) \\ &= \sum_{\zeta=+,-} \sum_{s=+,-} N_{\zeta s}(\varepsilon) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

with

$$N_{\zeta s}(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2\pi \hbar^2 v_F^2} |\varepsilon| \Theta(|\varepsilon| - ||U| - \zeta s \lambda_{SO}|). \quad (9)$$

The DOS is represented in Fig. 19 for various field strengths. Without external field $U = 0$ the DOS is zero in the gap region $|\varepsilon| < \lambda_{SO}$ and increases

linearly for $|\varepsilon| > \lambda_{SO}$. With applied field an additional steplike behavior appears at $|\varepsilon| = \lambda_{SO}$. The occurrence of a second conduction and valence band and the gap variation are visible in Fig. 19 as steps and vanishing DOS, respectively.

3.2. Functionalized Xenes

3.2.1. Hydrogenation

The alternately but fully hydrogenated group-IV sheets, the Xanes tend to have the chairlike geometry in the ground state [23, 89, 91, 93]. This geometry is displayed in Fig. 6. The resulting QP band structures of graphane, silicane, germanane, and stanane [91, 93] are displayed in Fig. 20 for the fully DFT-relaxed atomic arrangements within the G_0W_0 approach starting from KS electronic states in GGA or LDA qualities. They are completely different from the band structures of the nonhydrogenated group-IV sheets, the Xenes, shown in Fig. 16 due to the almost sp^3 hybridization and the ionic IV-H bonds. The Dirac cones at the K or K' points disappear. Huge gaps of the order of 15 eV (CH) and 8 eV (SiH, GeH, SnH) [91, 93] are opened. Due to the hydrogenation the zero-gap or small-gap semiconductors transform into insulators with remarkably more or less direct gaps at the Γ point. Only the conduction band minimum at M in the BZ of silicene is slightly below the Γ minimum, while this valley is above the Γ one in germanene. The QP gap openings from DFT to GW are of the order of 2 eV (CH, SiH, GeH) or 1 eV (SnH). In detail (see also Table 4) the DFT-LDA values 3.5, 3.4, 3.4 eV (CH) [91, 95, 204, 229], 2.0, 2.36, 2.16, 2.19 eV (SiH), 1.4, 1.34 eV (GeH) [89, 91, 102, 229], 0.57 eV (SnH) [93] are increased to 6.1, 5.4 eV (CH) [91, 95, 204, 229], 3.8, 3.6, 4.07 eV (SiH) [89, 91, 229], 2.4 eV (GeH) [91],

and 1.63 eV (SnH) [93], respectively.

The gap opening at Γ is accompanied by a drastic reduction of the electron affinity A due to hydrogenation, from the DFT values 4.2, 4.6, 4.7 eV to the GW ones 0.3, 2.5, 3.3 eV along the row C, Si, Ge [91]. The small A value for graphane is not unexpected, since hydrogenated diamond surfaces even show a negative affinity [230]. The general reason of the A lowering is the presence of compensating IV-H bond dipoles on the top and below the bottom of the buckled group-IV sheet. Their different influence is a consequence of their orientation, i.e., the electron transfer along the IV-H bonds. While C atoms are more electronegative than H ones, the opposite holds for Si and Ge [24]. The resulting strong hydrogen contribution to the conduction band minimum in graphane is illustrated in Fig. 21. The strong hydrogen influence on the lowest conduction bands is obvious from Fig. 21b but also Fig. 21c. The band edges of silicane and germanane, however, are determined by group-IV states (Figs. 22b and c). HSE studies suggest that the conduction band minimum arises from Si-H σ^* bonds in silicane [231].

Similar effects of the hydrogenation of silicongraphene to silicongraphane as of graphene and silicene to graphane and silicane, respectively, are illustrated in Fig. 23, despite the fact of a huge direct gap existing already at K in the hydrogenfree SiC sheet due to the polar Si-C bonds. After hydrogenation of the flat SiC sheet the direct gap appears at Γ with an absolute value only slightly below the graphane one. A value of A similar as for graphane is also observed for the low electron affinities. The most interesting point, however, is the occurrence of different vacuum levels for the Si- and C-terminated sides of the sheet (see inset of Fig. 23) [78]. The values $A_C = 0.1$ eV and

$A_{\text{Si}} = 1.8$ eV differ significantly. Nevertheless, the difference does not mean that an energy gain and hence a perpetuum mobile is possible by emitting electrons from the C-terminated side and reabsorbing these electrons at the Si-terminated side. The electrons have to work against the inner dipole field [232].

3.2.2. Halogenation

Fully fluorinated graphene, fluorographene, and partially chlorinated graphene, chlorographene, have been successfully prepared [22, 79, 233, 234]. Theoretical investigations are also available [235]. The halogenation by F, Cl, Br or I of other group-IV systems has been only studied theoretically [84, 85, 86, 87, 236, 237]. Band structures are displayed in Fig. 24 for two examples, iodine-decorated germanene and fluorostanene. Two general tendencies are obvious. Similar to the Xanes a huge gap is opened at K. However, in contrast to the Xanes a small indirect gap is opened near Γ with the VBM slightly away from Γ . The upper valence band exhibits a typical Mexican-hat- or camel-back-like dispersion, which indicates some state mixing and parity exchange due to SOC and the formation of an inverted gap. This dispersion already gives strong hints for a topological insulator and, therefore, the QSH phase. Without SOC the gap disappears and the band structure indicates a zero-gap semiconductor [86]. In the case of the examples in Fig. 24 the indirect gap values are 310.6 meV (GeI) and 287.7 (SnF) [87].

In halogenated silicene and other Xanes the calculated direct gaps at Γ are usually significantly larger. For instance, for fluorosilicene it is in the range of 0.49, 0.70 eV [229, 237], 1.47 eV [236], 1.6 eV [238], 2.33, 2.76 eV [229, 237] in dependence of the used XC functional PBE, sX-LDA, HSE,

GW_0 . Silicene covered by Cl, Br, and I gives rise to a gap of 1.98, 1.95, and 1.19 eV, respectively, in sX-LDA quality [236]. In the Ge case the gaps are much smaller. Upon chemisorption of Cl, Br, and I on germanene the SOC-induced gap at Γ is found to be 86, 237 and 162 meV, respectively, in DFT-PBE [85]. For iodinated germanene other computations give 0.31 (0.40) eV in PBE and 0.30 (0.43) eV in HSE for the indirect (direct) gap [239]. More details on gaps of halogenated germanene are listed in Table 3. One word of caution is however needed studying Table 3. The semilocal PBE XC functional suggests that halogenated germanene sheets are prototypes of large-gap 2D TIs, in contrast to the results of the HSE functional, which only show that GeI is a TI. The reason for this discrepancy could be the general trend for overestimation of band inversion tendency by local and semilocal XC functionals as demonstrated for the 3D TI α -Sn [240]. The trend for a smaller Γ gap along the row C \rightarrow Sn is hardly visible from Fig. 24b, but seems to be confirmed by a vanishing gap for SnF within DFT-PBE [84].

3.3. Xenes on substrates

3.3.1. Hybridization

As discussed in Sec. 3.1.2, an unmistakable fingerprint of Xenes are the linear bands crossing at K in the 1×1 BZ (without SOC) accompanied by forming Dirac cones, if the 2D wavevector is varied around such a zone boundary point. Therefore, the observation of linear bands for Xenes deposited on substrates may be considered as clear evidence of the survival of the (buckled) honeycomb arrangement of the group-IV atoms and only a minor electron exchange between overlayer and substrate. The most direct experimental tool is a measurement of the photoelectron intensity map by ARPES, at

least for the occupied bands. Such maps from the simultaneous measurement of the number of photoelectrons, their energy, and their wavevector \mathbf{k} are plotted in Fig. 25. The positive values of the energies define the binding energy of valence electrons with respect to the Fermi level E_F . Results for the deposition of 3×3 silicene on 4×4 Ag(111) in Fig. 25a [105] and $\sqrt{7}\times\sqrt{7}$ germanene on 8×8 Au(111) in Fig. 25b [134] are depicted. They fairly convince in showing linear dispersions around the K point of the 1×1 silicene and germanene, respectively. A linear band is seemingly visible for silicene with a Fermi velocity of $v_F = 1.3 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ as well as for germanene with $v_F = 1.1 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, both much larger than the theoretical predictions for freestanding group-IV sheets in Table 1. The downshift of the Dirac point by 0.3 eV and 0.77 eV can be interpreted as the consequence of electron transfer from silver to silicene and gold to germanene, respectively.

Nevertheless, these results for silicene/Ag(111) as well as those from [106] have been questioned, in particular by electronic structure studies in the DFT framework [112, 116, 241, 242, 243, 244] but also other experimental studies [246]. A simple counter argument is that the seeming linear band down to -3 eV in Fig. 25a is unlikely [241]. Arguments against the above interpretation of experimentally observed linear silicene bands arise from calculated band structures in Fig. 26. The band structure of the peeled-off silicene sheet does only show p_z -derived parabolic bands around Γ , onto which the K point of the smaller 1×1 BZ is folded, together with a pronounced gap. The expected Dirac cones do not survive [112]. Very strong theoretical findings concern a strong hybridization between the Si and Ag electronic states. Several arguments are given: (i) The surface-projected bulk Ag sp band has a similar

dispersion as the linear band observed by ARPES [116, 241]. (ii) The linear dispersion results from the hybridization between silicene, Si p states, and the substrate, the Ag s orbitals, since such states disappear for the clean Ag(111) surface [243]. (iii) The linear band arises from the wavevector dispersion of Ag(111) substrate states, somewhat modified by the interaction with the silicene, but not from the original silicene bands near the Dirac point [244]. Even, the downshift of the Dirac point can be explained by the adsorbate-substrate interaction as opening of a gap (see also Fig. 26). These findings are underlined by other angle-resolved valence band and core level photoemission data [245], which demonstrate that the linear band attributed e.g. in [105] to states with Dirac fermion character are derived from Ag(111) interface and bulk states.

A trial to interpret the findings of a linear band in Fig. 26 is made in Fig. 27. Within the bands of the 3×3 silicene/ 4×4 Ag(111) system, two quasi-linear features are visible, one is derived from Si states, the other one from Ag states. The linear Si features show a band slope with a Fermi velocity $v_F = 4.6 \times 10^5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, close to the values in Table 1. However, the Dirac point is 1.2 eV below the Fermi level E_F in clear contrast to the measured 0.3 eV [105]. On the other hand, the linear dispersion (the dashed green line) starts 0.3 eV below E_F and gives a Fermi velocity of $v_F = 1.3 \times 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ close to the measurement [105]. However, this band is mainly Ag-derived. This conclusion is supported by the wave function in Fig. 27c. It almost represents a bulk Ag state.

Other experimental studies support the above theoretical interpretations. It is argued that the assigned π -like silicene state actually derives from an

interface Ag state of free-electron-like character. The overall picture is consistent with a metallic hybrid band, exhibiting a nearly linear variation across the K_{Ag} point with the middle point M_{Ag} (see BZ in Fig. 25a) [246, 247]. However, in a more recent linear dichroism ARPES study with p -polarized light [248] an opposite interpretation is given. It is based on the idea that the silver substrate gives rise to a periodic manipulation of the electronic structure of 3×3 silicene compared to the freestanding 1×1 silicene. The Dirac cones of the latter 2D system are modified by substrate-induced periodic perturbations, which are related to the 3×3 superstructure. The observed Dirac cones are mainly derived from the original cones at the K and K' points of freestanding 1×1 silicene.

Summarizing, there seems to be a controversy that asks for further theoretical and experimental investigations. The standard interpretation, that the hybridization between the 3×3 silicene with the 4×4 Ag(111) suppresses the formation of linearly dispersed π bands with Dirac cone feature, stands against the only observation of Dirac cones by p -polarized light and, hence, the indication that the linear bands are essentially derived from Si p_z orbitals. Interestingly, also first-principles studies of germanene on metal substrates including Au(111) [144] suggest that the intrinsic properties of this group-IV sheet almost survive on Au and Ag substrates, in contrast to the Dirac cones of silicene on silver. The deposition of a silicon monolayer on a Au(111) substrate is obviously an excellent attempt to prepare a silicene sheet [249]. The two elements tend to phase separation [250] because of the Si surface energies are much below those of gold. Indeed, ARPES measurements show unambiguous evidence for the existence of Dirac fermions in the Si adlayer

by the conical dispersion of the highest valence band, although its Fermi velocity $v_F = 1.3 \times 10^6$ m/s is much larger than that of freestanding silicene.

3.3.2. *vdW interaction*

In general, metallic substrates such as Ag(111) tend to strong interaction with the group-IV overlayer [112, 127]. Options to avoid this strong hybridization may be the choice of insulating substrates [148, 154, 155, 175, 180], which however ask for detailed discussions of their surface states. They are strongly driven by first-principles calculations. Several examples can be given. The stabilization of the monolayer honeycomb structure of silicene and germanene with preserving of the Dirac cones is suggested on the wide-gap material Al_2O_3 [178]. On the Al-terminated $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(0001)$ surface the buckled honeycomb structure survives, despite an overlayer-substrate binding comparable that on Ag(111). The resulting Dirac cones are, however, gapped with gap values of 0.4 and 0.3 eV, respectively. These values only indicate a minor or intermediate overlayer-substrate interaction.

This idea has been also studied for silicene on a modified substrate, a monolayer of aluminum oxide, a 2D insulator with a gap of about 8.2 eV, as displayed in Fig. 28a [179]. The GW band structure of the silicene/ Al_2O_3 system in Fig. 28a only exhibits silicene-derived bands in the wide Al_2O_3 gap. The nearly linear π - and π^* -bands emerge into a Dirac point folded onto the Γ point of the smaller BZ of the 3×3 system. Because of the broken inversion symmetry, the weak vdW interaction between the silicene and alumina sheets partially lifts the band degeneracy. In the absence of SOC no gap appears at the Dirac point. There is however a splitting of the second formerly degenerated bands. The Fermi velocity $v_F = 4.94$ (6.4) $\times 10^5$ m/s in DFT

(GW) quality is only slightly different from the values $v_F = 5.75 (6.1) \times 10^5$ m/s of freestanding silicene (see also Table 1). Interestingly, monolayer germanene has been successfully fabricated on a semiconducting germanium film with the support of a Ag(111) substrate [155]. Its nearly linear energy-momentum relation near the Dirac point with a Fermi velocity of $(3.7 \pm 0.3) \times 10^5$ m/s is derived from pronounced quasiparticle interference patterns in a $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ superstructure measured by means of STS. The symmetry-breaking potential opens a small gap of 78 meV (from accompanying calculations). Qualitatively similar results have been predicted by DFT-GGA calculations for silicene deposited on H-passivated Ge(111)1×1 surfaces [51]. Due to the vdW interaction with the substrate the Fermi velocity is slightly reduced to 4.2×10^5 m/s and a gap of 66 meV is opened.

Another interesting substrate is the natural cleavage $\text{CaF}_2(111)$ surface (see Fig. 10b) with an experimental value of 12.1 eV for the fundamental gap of the bulk. The DFT-GGA band structure of the resulting silicene/ $\text{CaF}_2(111)$ system is plotted versus the hexagonal BZ in Fig. 28b [154]. The surface triple layer F-Ca-F makes the substrate widely inert. The silicene-derived linear π - and π^* -bands occur in the fundamental gap and form Dirac cones around the K point. The Fermi velocity is about 4.9×10^5 m/s and the gap opening due to the weakly interacting substrate amounts to 52 meV.

All these theoretical predictions have to be considered with care in the light of the applied approximations, XC, vdW and numerical approaches. Examples are the contradictory *ab initio* DFT results obtained for silicene on an hBN substrate. The nine different stackings studied in [251] lead to band gaps in the range of 27-39 meV. The Fermi velocity of silicene is

reduced to 83-92% of the value of its freestanding counterpart (see Table 1). The buckling parameter $\Delta = 0.46 \text{ \AA}$ (see also Table 1) however remains uninfluenced by the stacking and the interaction with the substrate. Other studies [252] found an increase of the buckling to $\Delta = 0.54 \text{ \AA}$, while the energy gap and the Fermi velocity remain largely unchanged compared to freestanding silicene.

4. Optical spectra

4.1. General considerations

4.1.1. Optical conductivity

Optical spectroscopies can help for a better understanding of the group-IV sheets and their functionalized derivatives. The opacity, reflectivity, and transmittivity of graphene have been studied in the infrared-to-visible spectral range [6, 7]. Its optical sheet conductivity has been also measured in the infrared-to-ultraviolet region, e.g. applying the spectroscopic ellipsometry [253, 254]. The optical properties of silicene-like overlayers on Ag(111) or Ag(110) have been investigated by means of reflectance anisotropy spectroscopy (RAS) and surface differential reflectivity spectroscopy (SDRS) in a wide range of photon energies 1-5 eV (see [255] and references therein and illustration in Fig. 29). The optical properties of germanene, in particular the absorbance over visible wavelengths, were investigated by diffuse reflectance absorption [98]. In the case of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) frequently, in a wide energy range, the optical dielectric function is derived from reflection spectra combined with a Kramers-Kronig analysis [256] or directly by means of spectroscopic ellipsometry [257, 258].

The linear optical properties of three-dimensional systems are characterized by the frequency-dependent dielectric function or tensor $\epsilon_{ij}(\omega)$. This also holds for the modelling of 2D objects within the superlattice approach (see Fig. 2b and Sec. 3.1). Within the independent-(quasi)particle approach (IQA) [259] the corresponding Kubo expression can be formulated as Ehrenreich-Cohen formula in longitudinal gauge (in cgs units) [193, 260, 261]

$$\epsilon_{ij}^{\text{SL}}(\omega) = \delta_{ij} - \frac{4\pi e^2 \hbar^2}{m^2} \frac{1}{AL} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\nu, \nu'} w(\mathbf{k}) \frac{p_{\nu\nu'}^i(\mathbf{k}) p_{\nu'\nu}^j(\mathbf{k})}{[\epsilon_{\nu}(\mathbf{k}) - \epsilon_{\nu'}(\mathbf{k})]^2} \frac{f(\epsilon_{\nu'}(\mathbf{k})) - f(\epsilon_{\nu}(\mathbf{k}))}{\epsilon_{\nu'}(\mathbf{k}) - \epsilon_{\nu}(\mathbf{k}) + \hbar\omega + i\eta} \quad (10)$$

with the Fermi occupation numbers $f(\epsilon) = [1 + \exp((\epsilon - \mu)/k_B T)]^{-1}$ (μ - chemical potential of electrons, T - sample temperature), the momentum matrix elements $p_{\nu\nu'}^j(\mathbf{k}) = \langle \nu\mathbf{k} | p_j | \nu'\mathbf{k} \rangle$ with Bloch-Pauli spinors $|\nu\mathbf{k}\rangle$ (see Sec. 3.1.1), QP band energies $\epsilon_{\nu}(\mathbf{k})$, the \mathbf{k} -point weight $w(\mathbf{k})$, the 2D unit-cell area A , the lattice constant L of the superlattice (SL) used to simulate the 2D objects (see e.g. Fig. 2b) and $\eta \rightarrow +0$ (as the broadening parameter).

In the limit of fully occupied valence (v) bands and empty conduction (c) bands, the diagonal elements of the dielectric tensor can be also calculated including excitonic effects according to [193, 201]

$$\epsilon_{jj}^{\text{SL}}(\omega) = 1 + \frac{4\pi e^2 \hbar^2}{m^2 \Omega} \sum_{\Lambda} \left| \sum_{c,v,\mathbf{k}} \frac{p_{cv}^{j*}(\mathbf{k})}{\epsilon_c(\mathbf{k}) - \epsilon_v(\mathbf{k})} A_{\Lambda}(c\nu\mathbf{k}) \right|^2 \times \left[\frac{1}{E_{\Lambda} - \hbar\omega - i\eta} + \frac{1}{E_{\Lambda} + \hbar\omega + i\eta} \right] \quad (11)$$

with the eigenvalues E_{Λ} and eigenvectors $A_{\Lambda}(c\nu\mathbf{k})$ of the electron-hole pairs (excitons) between valence bands (holes) and conduction bands (electrons). Λ represents the set of the pair quantum numbers. Ω denotes the volume

of the artificial crystal with $\Omega = LA/w(\mathbf{k})$ in the case of a homogeneous distribution of the \mathbf{k} points. The two-particle Schrödinger equation in the single-particle Bloch-Pauli basis reads as [193, 201]

$$\sum_{c',v',\mathbf{k}'} H(cv\mathbf{k}, c'v'\mathbf{k}') A_{\Lambda}(c'v'\mathbf{k}') = E_{\Lambda} A_{\Lambda}(cv\mathbf{k}) \quad (12)$$

with the pair Hamiltonian

$$H(cv\mathbf{k}, c'v'\mathbf{k}') = [\varepsilon_c(\mathbf{k}) - \varepsilon_v(\mathbf{k})] \delta_{cc'} \delta_{vv'} \delta_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} - W_{vv'}^{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} + \bar{v}_{v'c'}^{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}, \quad (13)$$

where the matrix elements of the (attractive) statically screened Coulomb potential $W_{vv'}^{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ and the (repulsive) bare electron-hole exchange $\bar{v}_{v'c'}^{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'}$ appear.

In 2D systems, such as Xenes and their functionalized derivatives with hexagonal and square Bravais lattices, i.e., macroscopic in-plane isotropy, only diagonal elements of the dielectric tensor $\epsilon_{jj}^{\text{SL}}(\omega)$ are nonzero. Consequently, one only has to consider elements $jj = xx = yy \hat{=}$ for in-plane light polarization and $jj = zz \hat{=}$ for out-of-plane light polarization, respectively, where x and y are in-plane Cartesian coordinates, while the z -axis points in normal direction. For sufficiently large superlattice periods $L \gg a$ only one layer of \mathbf{k} points is taken within the 3D BZ, usually a $N \times N \times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack mesh with N much larger than in the case of total energy computations [50]. Since a superlattice unit cell contains a vacuum region of thickness $L - \delta$ with δ as the effective extent of the 2D object in normal direction (see Fig. 2b), the dielectric functions $\epsilon_{jj}^{\text{SL}}(\omega)$ of the superlattice arrangement can be directly related to dielectric functions $\epsilon_{jj}^{\text{2D}}(\omega)$ of the 2D crystal.

In the case of graphene the sheet thickness may be identified with $\delta = 3.35 \text{ \AA}$, corresponding to the carbon layer distance in graphite [262]. Then the

limit $\delta \ll \lambda$ with $\lambda = 2\pi c/\omega$, the wavelength of light, is fulfilled. The tensor $\hat{\epsilon}^{2D}(\omega)$ with two independent components can be related to the superlattice quantity $\hat{\epsilon}^{SL}(\omega)$ within an effective medium theory [263] as

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{\parallel}^{2D}(\omega) &= 1 + \frac{L}{\delta} [\epsilon_{\parallel}^{SL}(\omega) - 1], \\ \frac{1}{\epsilon_{\perp}^{2D}(\omega)} &= 1 + \frac{L}{\delta} \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon_{\perp}^{SL}(\omega)} - 1 \right].\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

In the independent-(quasi)particle limit, the 2D dielectric functions do not depend on the superlattice period L , however on the sheet thickness δ . In addition, the quantity $\delta [\epsilon_{\parallel}^{2D}(\omega) - 1]$ is independent of δ . In order to deal with thickness-independent quantities, instead of the 2D dielectric tensor (14), based on a volumetric response function, the 2D optical conductivity tensor $\hat{\sigma}_{2D}(\omega)$ should be studied. These sheet response functions become (in cgs units) [261]

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) &= -\frac{i\omega}{4\pi} L [\epsilon_{\parallel}^{SL}(\omega) - 1], \\ \sigma_{2D}^{\perp}(\omega) &= -\frac{i\omega}{4\pi} L \left[1 - \frac{1}{\epsilon_{\perp}^{SL}(\omega)} \right].\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

The L -independence can be easily proven by applying the IPA or IQA (10) in (15).

The different relationships between $\hat{\epsilon}^{SL}(\omega)$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{2D}(\omega)$ in (15) for different light polarizations indicate the huge optical anisotropy in the case of graphene-like group-IV crystals [201, 261]. It is illustrated in Fig. 29 for graphene and silicene within the IPA and without SOC. The out-of-plane components are almost zero in the low-energy region and the absorption edge for out-of-plane light polarization is significantly blueshifted compared with the in-plane spectra. This is a consequence of two effects: (i) The optical

transitions between π - and π^* -like bands are only allowed for in-plane light polarization. (ii) Strong local-field effects modify the out-of-plane spectrum, as discussed in literature for graphene [201, 264]. In general, the spectral features being visible in Fig. 30 can be most easily related to the electronic structure discussed in Sec. 3.1 considering the real part of the in-plane conductivity $\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)$. The low-energy plateau $Re[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)] = \sigma_0$ ($\omega \rightarrow 0$) is a consequence of optical transitions between the linear π - and π^* -bands around the K and K' points. The first van Hove singularity near 4.0 (graphene) and 1.6 eV (silicene) is related to optical transitions near to the M point, where the orbital character of the lowest conduction and highest valence band changes. The second pronounced van Hove singularity around 13.9 (graphene) and 3.3 eV (silicene), respectively, is essentially related to $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions between valence and conduction bands near Γ .

4.1.2. Reflectance, transmittance, and absorbance

In optical experiments, the 2D objects investigated are not freestanding but grown on a substrate or deposited on a 3D dielectric. For grazing incidence of light, in Fig. 31 the three-layer situation is illustrated for the light source in vacuum and an infinite, isotropic crystal, which supports the 2D object that is characterized by the tensors $\hat{\sigma}_{2D}(\omega)$ (15) and $\hat{\epsilon}^{2D}(\omega)$ (14) as well as the effective sheet thickness δ .

The coupling of the electromagnetic field depends on the characterization of the optical properties of the sheet. If the sheet is characterized as a conducting interface between vacuum and dielectric with $\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)$, an in-plane current density $j_{2D}(\omega)$ appears according to Ohm's law. The action of this current can be described by modifying the electromagnetic boundary condi-

tions [261]. However, the description as conducting interface only allows to describe correctly the effect of in-plane electric fields, i.e., normal incidence of light. To include also the out-of-plane polarization the transfer-matrix method using the tensor $\hat{\epsilon}^{2D}(\omega)$ and the subsequent limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$ can be applied. Complicated expressions for absorbance $A(\omega)$, transmittance $T(\omega)$, and reflectance $R(\omega)$ result for s - and p -polarized grazing-incident light [261].

Therefore, we focus on the normal incidence, i.e., the angle $\theta_1 = 0$ in Fig. 31. The optical properties of the substrate are described by a complex refraction index n with $n^2 = \epsilon_2(\omega)$. It follows Fresnel-like expressions [19, 261, 265]

$$\begin{aligned} R(\omega) &= \left| \frac{1 - n - \tilde{\sigma}}{1 + n + \tilde{\sigma}} \right|^2, \\ T(\omega) &= \frac{4\text{Re}n}{|1 + n + \tilde{\sigma}|^2}, \\ A(\omega) &= \frac{4\text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}}{|1 + n + \tilde{\sigma}|^2}, \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where the dimensionless abbreviation $\tilde{\sigma} = \frac{4\pi}{c}\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)$ is introduced. Thereby it holds $R(\omega) + T(\omega) + A(\omega) = 1$. In the case of insulating substrates, the frequency dependence of the dielectric function and the absorption of the substrate can be omitted. Assuming that the effect of the atomically thin sheet is small, more precisely $|\tilde{\sigma}| \ll |n - 1|$, expressions (16) can be linearized resulting in

$$\begin{aligned} R(\omega) &= \left(\frac{n - 1}{n + 1} \right)^2 \left(1 + \frac{4\text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}}{n^2 - 1} \right), \\ T(\omega) &= \frac{4n}{(n + 1)^2} \left(1 - \frac{2\text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}}{n + 1} \right), \\ A(\omega) &= \frac{4\text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}}{(n + 1)^2}, \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Expressions (16) and (17) suggest how the SDRS idea (see Fig. 30) can be applied to measure the optical properties of a 2D crystal on the substrate characterized by the refraction index n . One may measure the reflectance contrast $\Delta R(\omega)/R(\omega) = [R_{\text{layer}}(\omega) - R(\omega)]/R(\omega)$ with $R_{\text{layer}}(\omega)$ [$R(\omega)$] as the measured reflection spectrum for the substrate covered by the 2D crystal [pure substrate]. From the Fresnel formula for normal incidence (17) one derives

$$\text{Re} \left[\sigma_{2\text{D}}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] = \frac{c}{4\pi} \frac{n^2 - 1}{4} \frac{\Delta R(\omega)}{R(\omega)}.$$

In such a way $A(\omega)$ (16), the absorbance of a freestanding atomic layer, has been measured for graphene supported by a SiO_2 substrate, more precisely a SiO_2 film prepared on top of a Si wafer, by means of the reflectance contrast modified by $(n^2 - 1)$ [7, 254].

According to (16) and (17), the main contribution to the absorption of the layered system happens in the 2D object as indicated by the proportionality to $\text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}$. This is obvious in the freestanding case from (16) with $n = 1$, $R(\omega) = 0$ (small in general), $T(\omega) = 1 - \text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}$, and $A(\omega) = \text{Re}\tilde{\sigma}$. However, for $n > 1$, expressions (16) and (17) show that the optical spectra $R(\omega)$, $T(\omega)$, and $A(\omega)$ will be substantially influenced by the light refraction in the supporting dielectric. In the case of metallic substrates the situation is more complex and expressions (16) have to be applied. In Fig. 32 we illustrate the optical properties of graphene, silicene, germanene, and stanene only without support, i.e., for $n = 1$. The spectral features, in particular the van Hove singularities and the plateau for $\omega \rightarrow 0$, appear also in the $A(\omega)$ and $T(\omega) - 1$ curves. Most remarkable is the huge effect of a single atomic layer on optical spectra. Only the reflectance $R(\omega)$ is small. It vanishes between the van

Have singularities, but even in their environment $R(\omega)$ amounts less than 10 % of $A(\omega)$. A word of caution is needed. In literature, one finds results of *ab initio* calculations for the optical conductivity and reflectivity, e.g. in [266], which are different from those presented in Fig. 32. The reason is that, in contrast to Fig. 32, bulk properties of the superlattice arrangements of the 2D objects are displayed but not the optical properties of an isolated, freestanding group-IV sheet.

4.2. Independent-(quasi)particle picture

4.2.1. Joint band structure and density of states

In Fig. 33 the interband transition energies $\Delta\varepsilon_{cv}(\mathbf{k}) = \varepsilon_c(\mathbf{k}) - \varepsilon_v(\mathbf{k})$ between conduction and valence bands are displayed together with the joint density of states (JDOS) of graphene, silicene, and germanene applying KS electronic structures derived with the PBE functional. For small energies also interband Dirac cones appear at the K (and K') points. They are accompanied by a JDOS, which varies linearly in energy in the low-energy region. For intermediate and higher energies the extrema or saddle points of the interband energies at high-symmetry points and lines become visible. They give rise to van Hove singularities in the JDOS. They will be investigated below.

The interband band structures in Fig. 33 in the limit of vanishing energies clearly indicate Dirac cones formed by linear bands $2\hbar v_F|\boldsymbol{\kappa}|$ with relative wavevectors $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}_{K(K')}$ with respect to the K (K') point. Of course, with rising energy, far from the Dirac point, they become anisotropically deformed. This anisotropy is obvious comparing the interband energies along the high-symmetry lines KM and K Γ .

4.2.2. Low-frequency limit: Relation to Sommerfeld finestructure constant

The Dirac cones near K and K' indicate similarities of the bands in a small vicinity around a Dirac point. The similarity is obvious in Fig. 34a after band renormalization with $\hbar v_F \pi / a$, including the two parameters v_F and a listed in Table 1. Indeed, in energy units $\hbar v_F \pi / a$ the lowest conduction and highest valence bands of graphene, silicene, and germanene are rather equal along the high-symmetry lines KM and K Γ . A similar behavior is observed in Fig. 34b for the averaged in-plane matrix element squares for transitions between the bands displayed in Fig. 34a. The normalization here is $\frac{1}{2} m^2 v_F^2$. At K and K' even the matrix elements are equal, each of them being equal to its normalization factor and, hence, independent of the group-IV element.

The value of an averaged matrix element square of $\frac{1}{2} m^2 v_F^2$ is a consequence of the wave functions of the π - and π^* -bands for a \mathbf{k} vector very close to \mathbf{k}_K , shown in Figs. 34c and d. The influence of the layer buckling on the p_z -like orbital character is visible. The similarity of the wave functions suggests that the interband matrix element at vanishing interband energy can be replaced by an intraband matrix element, apart from a phase factor, as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=x,y} |p_{cv}^j(\mathbf{k}_K)|^2 \\ &= \frac{m^2}{\hbar^2} \sum_{j=x,y} \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial \kappa_j} \Delta \varepsilon_{cv}(\mathbf{k}_K + \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \right|_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}=0}^2 = (m v_F)^2 \sum_{j=x,y} \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial \kappa_j} \kappa \right|^2 = (m v_F)^2. \end{aligned}$$

The findings in Fig. 34 suggest an approximate treatment of the optical conductivity (15) with the representation (10). In the limit $\omega \rightarrow 0^+$ only the lowest conduction and highest valence band as well as small wavevector deviations $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ from the K (or K') point \mathbf{k}_K (or $\mathbf{k}_{K'}$) contribute. In total, the vicinities of one K and one K' point contribute equally. If only fully occupied

or completely empty twofold-degenerate bands are assumed, it follows for low photon energies ($\omega \rightarrow 0^+$) [267, 268]

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Re} \left[\sigma_{2\text{D}}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] \\ &= \frac{4\pi e^2}{m^2 \omega} \int \frac{d^2 \boldsymbol{\kappa}}{(2\pi)^2} \frac{1}{2} \left[|p_{cv}^x(\mathbf{k}_K + \boldsymbol{\kappa})|^2 + |p_{cv}^y(\mathbf{k}_K + \boldsymbol{\kappa})|^2 \right] \delta(\Delta\varepsilon_{cv}(\mathbf{k}_K + \boldsymbol{\kappa}) - \hbar\omega). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

With results of Fig. 34, constant momentum matrix element and linearly varying interband energy, the $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ -integration can be easily performed. One finds

$$\text{Re} \left[\sigma_{2\text{D}}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] = \frac{e^2}{4\hbar} = \sigma_0 = \frac{c}{4} \alpha \quad (19)$$

with the Sommerfeld finestructure constant $\alpha = \frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \approx \frac{1}{137}$. A universal conductivity $\sigma_0 = \frac{e^2}{4\hbar}$ appears [6]. Consequently, with (19) the absorbance (17) of a freestanding group-IV honeycomb crystal becomes $A(\omega) = \pi\alpha$.

Indeed, this fact has been observed experimentally for graphene [6, 7]. The finestructure constant α defines the visual transparency of graphene. The measurements of the optical conductivity or the opacity in the infrared (IR)-to-visible spectral range [6] show a plateau. Also reflectivity and transmittivity experiments in the IR between 0.2–1.2 eV, in particular above 0.5 eV, [7] show flat optical absorbance and reflectance spectra. Summarizing, the absorbance of an atomically thin layer of group-IV atoms is defined by the Sommerfeld finestructure constant α . $A(0) = \pi\alpha$ means that, despite only one atom thick, the group-IV honeycomb layers absorb a significant fraction ($\pi\alpha \hat{=} 2.3\%$) of the incident light. The absorbance $A(\omega)$ and the opacity, $1 - T(\omega)$, are practically independent of wavelength in a wide range, whose extent however is sensitive to the group-IV element (see Fig. 33). The described spectral features have been partly observed for silicene-on-sapphire

(see Sec. 2.3.3). The advent of the Xene-on-sapphire technique has been identified as a novel paradigm in photonics [269]. This scenario was first theoretically conceptualized [178, 179]. Evidence of silicene-on-sapphire relies on the optical conductivity of a silicon film at the extreme atomic thickness with a plateau at low energies, a small absorption peak around 1.4 eV, and an almost linearly rising effect toward 3 eV [176].

The discussed spectral behavior is visible in all types of theoretical spectra for freestanding Xenenes in Fig. 32 but especially in Fig. 35a. It shows the absorption onset for graphene, silicene, and germanene without SOC in the independent-particle approach. The limit $A(\omega) = \pi\alpha$ is clearly demonstrated. However, higher optical transitions, mainly at the M point with a saddle-point van Hove singularity, appear below 2 eV but, in addition, in the germanene case at Γ also a minimum M_0 van Hove singularity around 0.9 eV. The inset in Fig. 35a shows that the weak absorption increase varies actually quadratically with the photon energy.

In general, the absorption features related to the van Hove singularities depicted in Fig. 33 are illustrated in Fig. 35b. In the chosen interval of photon energies for graphene there is only the M_1 saddle point visible near 4.0 eV. This spectral feature shifts down in energy to 1.6 eV (silicene) and 1.8 eV (germanene), respectively. In germanene, the lowest M_0 singularity shifts down in energy toward 1 eV. Higher-energy van Hove singularities are visible at 3.8 eV and 4.3 eV at Γ , M, K (silicene) or even more at 3.1, 3.8, and 4.3 eV at Γ , M (germanene). These calculated lineshapes mean that for low-photon energies the absorbance and the real part of the in-plane optical conductivity are not only independent of the group-IV element, but also of

the actual treatment of exchange and correlation in the electronic structure calculation. Both quantities are universal for $\omega \rightarrow 0$, if SOC and excitonic effects are omitted. The universality of the dynamic conductivity (19) is a general behavior expected for ideal Dirac fermions.

4.2.3. Influence of SOC

In the discussion of optical properties in Sec. 4.2.2 the SOC has been omitted, in contrast to the electronic-structure findings in Sec. 3.1.2. According to that SOC especially modifies the bands near the Dirac points. The low-energy four-band model (4) takes SOC into account. For that reason we apply it to investigate the optical conductivity for small photon energies. Within the 4×4 matrix representations (4) and (7) the frequency-dependent complex conductivity (15) together with the independent-particle Kubo formula (10), now in transverse gauge, can be reformulated for $\omega \rightarrow 0$ as ($\eta \rightarrow 0^+$) [87, 226, 270]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}(\omega) = & \frac{ie^2}{\omega} \sum_{\zeta=+,-} \int \frac{d^2\boldsymbol{\kappa}}{(2\pi)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d\varepsilon}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d\varepsilon'}{2\pi} \frac{f(\varepsilon) - f(\varepsilon')}{\varepsilon - \varepsilon' + \hbar\omega + i\eta} \\ & \times \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\hat{V}_i(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon') \right] \left[\hat{V}_j(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon) \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

with matrices of spectral functions $\hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon)$ of type (7) and velocity matrices

$$\hat{V}_j(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) = \frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{\partial}{\partial \kappa_j} \hat{H}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) \quad (j = x, y). \quad (21)$$

In accordance with the restriction to low photon energies the original summation/integration over the entire BZ is divided into the contributions around the corner points K and K' (see Fig. 2c). Including the translational symmetry in reciprocal space the integration has to be performed in total around

one K point, $\mathbf{k}_K = \mathbf{k}_{K+}$, and one K' point, $\mathbf{k}_{K'} = \mathbf{k}_{K-}$. This is indicated in (20) by summing up over the two valleys $\zeta = +, -$ and the integration over deviations $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}_{K+,-}$. Interestingly, for finite temperatures the static limit of expression (20) can be also used to describe the electric conductivity and the electronic contribution to the thermal conductivity of 2D systems silicene, germanene, and stanene [55, 271, 272, 273].

Table 5 suggests the validity of the relation $\lambda_{SO} \gg \lambda_R$. Therefore, essentially the effect of the Kane-Mele SOC $\sim \lambda_{SO}$ has to be investigated. The Rashba contribution $\sim \lambda_R$ can be neglected. Instead of this SOC part, a vertical electric field characterized by the bias voltage U (see arrangement in Fig. 17a) is taken into account. In addition, we allow for a partial filling of the bands described by a chemical potential μ , the Fermi energy ε_F for vanishing temperature, which deviates from the energy zero $\mu = 0$, the energy position of the Dirac points in the limit of vanishing SOC. With the explicit representation of the spectral functions $\hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon)$ (7), the energy bands $\varepsilon_{\zeta\nu s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ (5), and the carrier velocities $\hat{V}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ (21) the two valleys $\zeta = +, -$ contribute equally to the optical conductivity (20). Because of $\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} [\sigma_{xx}(\omega) + \sigma_{yy}(\omega)]$ and $\sigma_{2D}^{\perp}(\omega) = \sigma_{zz}(\omega) = 0$ (within the model considerations) one may write

$$\begin{aligned}
& Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] \\
&= \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{e^2 v_F^2}{4\omega} \sum_{\zeta=+,-} \sum_{\nu,\nu'=+,-} \sum_{s=+,-} \int \frac{d^2\boldsymbol{\kappa}}{(2\pi)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} d\varepsilon [f(\varepsilon) - f(\varepsilon + \hbar\omega)] [\varepsilon(\varepsilon + \hbar\omega) - \lambda_s^2] \\
&\times \frac{1}{\varepsilon_{-\nu s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})\varepsilon_{-\nu' s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})} \delta(\varepsilon + \hbar\omega - \varepsilon_{-\nu s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})) \delta(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{-\nu' s}(\boldsymbol{\kappa})), \tag{22}
\end{aligned}$$

where the imaginary part is defined by the Kramers-Kronig relation

$$Im \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] = - \rlap{-}\int\limits_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\omega'}{\pi} \frac{Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega') \right]}{\omega' - \omega}. \quad (23)$$

In the low-temperature limit $T \rightarrow 0$ K, $f(\varepsilon) = \Theta(\mu - \varepsilon)$, with the eigenvalues (5), the integrations and summations in (22) and (23) yield with $\lambda_s = \lambda_{SO} + s|U|$ and $\max = \max(|\mu|, |\lambda_s|)$ (see [225] for $U = 0$ and [273] for $U \neq 0$ but $\lambda_{SO} = 0$)

$$\begin{aligned} Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] &= \sigma_0 \sum_{s=+,-} \left\{ 2 \frac{|\mu|^2 - \lambda_s^2}{|\mu|} \delta(\hbar\omega) \Theta(|\mu| - |\lambda_s|) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \left(\frac{2\lambda_s}{\hbar\omega} \right)^2 \right] \Theta(|\hbar\omega| - 2\max) \right\}, \\ Im \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] &= \text{sgn}(\omega) \frac{1}{\pi} \sigma_0 \sum_{s=+,-} \left\{ 2 \frac{\mu^2 - \lambda_s^2}{\hbar|\omega||\mu|} \Theta(|\mu| - |\lambda_s|) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \left(\frac{2\lambda_s}{\hbar\omega} \right)^2 \right] \ell n \frac{2\max + \hbar|\omega|}{|2\max - \hbar|\omega||} - \left(\frac{2\lambda_s}{\hbar\omega} \right)^2 \frac{\hbar|\omega|}{2\max} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The first term in the expressions (24) for the real and imaginary parts of the in-plane optical conductivity are due to intraband contributions. They vanish if the chemical potential μ lies in the fundamental gap, $|\mu| < |\lambda_-|$. This limit is considered to illustrate the more important interband contributions. Without external electric field, they are displayed in Fig. 36a for germanene, as calculated within the HSE06 framework. Its spectral behavior is identical with the analytic expression (24), $Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] = \sigma_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{2\lambda_{SO}}{\hbar\omega} \right)^2 \right] \Theta(\hbar|\omega| - 2\lambda_{SO})$ [17]. Below the fundamental gap, $\hbar\omega < E_g = 2\lambda_{SO}$, the (low-temperature) absorption vanishes, while for $\hbar\omega > E_g$ the absorption is significantly in-

creased to $Re[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(E_g/\hbar + 0^+)] = 2\sigma_0$ but recovers for higher photon energies the plateau value σ_0 observed for vanishing SOC in (19). The higher energy features above $\hbar\omega > 0.7$ eV in Fig. 36a are due to higher interband transitions of M_1 saddle-point type not included in the electronic structure model (4) underlying the conductivity (24). The lineshape modification $\sim \left[1 + \left(\frac{2\lambda_{SO}}{\hbar\omega}\right)^2\right]$ just above the absorption edge is a consequence of the strong SOC-induced \mathbf{k} dispersion of the optical matrix element near K as illustrated in Fig. 36b. The imaginary part of the interband conductivity in (24) shows a linear behavior $Im[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)] = \frac{1}{\pi}\sigma_0\frac{\hbar\omega}{\lambda_{SO}}$ for vanishing frequencies.

The electronic structure model (4) also includes the influence of a vertical bias U . Interestingly, its effect on the optical properties in (24) can be simply interpreted in terms of a renormalization of the Kane-Mele SOC contribution $\sim \lambda_{SO}$. Instead of the SOC coupling constant λ_{SO} , one has to deal with two coupling constants $\lambda_s = \lambda_{SO} + s|U|$ in dependence of the orientation of the spins in the spin-split bands in the presence of the external field U . As a consequence the field-free absorption edge $\hbar\omega = E_g$ splits into two at photon energies $\hbar\omega = 2|\lambda_-|$ and $\hbar\omega = 2|\lambda_+|$ indicating the field-induced lift of the spin degeneracy of the bands near the Dirac points. Another interesting effect is also expressed in (24), the influence of the band filling on the optical properties. First, an intraband absorption appears at nearly zero frequencies if, indeed, the chemical potential is shifted into one or even two conduction or valence bands. Second, there is also a modification of the interband contribution by shifting the absorption edge from $E_g = 2\lambda_{SO}$ to $2|\mu|$, if $|\mu| > \lambda_{SO}$. Due to the filling of the conduction band with electrons or the filling of the valence band with holes the optical transitions near K or K' are blocked

by the occupation number factor in expression (20), i.e., by the so-called Pauli blocking. In highly doped, so-called degenerate 3D semiconductors the spectral consequence of this phenomenon is called Burstein-Moss effect [193].

4.2.4. Interlayer interaction

In Sec. 2.4 the atomic structure and layer stacking of multilayer group-IV systems have been investigated. The corresponding results suggest the possibility of manipulation of optical properties by deposition not only of one Xene layer but, in general, of more sheets on top of each other. For hydrogenated bilayer silicene exceptional optoelectronic properties have been predicted [274]. The absorption strength can be tuned by a multilayer arrangement. For instance, the addition of further graphene layers increases the 2.3 % weakening of the transmitted light to $N \times 2.3$ % (with N the number of sheets) [6].

The Bernal-stacked bilayer graphene can be considered as a model system. In such an AB stack, half of the atoms lie directly over the center of a hexagon in the lower graphene sheet, and half of the atoms lie over an atomic site. No further rotation of the sheets against each other exists [275]. Including vdW interaction in the XC functional the optimization of the atomic geometry gives an interlayer spacing of 3.54 Å [276] not too far from the experimental distance 3.34 Å in graphite [262]. The main effect of the bilayer is doubling of the bands in Fig. 37a and their splitting due to the weak interaction between the sheets. Near K, besides the Dirac cones separated by a zero gap, a second pair of conduction and valence bands appears with a gap at this high-symmetry corner point. The consequences of the deviations from the electronic structure of isolated graphene sheets is displayed in Fig. 37b.

The influence of the intersheet interaction is weak in a wide frequency range. Only the saddle-point M_1 peak somewhat above 4 eV is modified in intensity. The gap opening in Fig. 37a induces a novel spectral feature for photon energies somewhat below 0.5 eV in Fig. 37b. This finding is in agreement with transmission measurements, which find a negative peak near $\hbar\omega = 0.4$ eV [277] or a positive structure at this energy in the absorbance [278].

Freestanding buckled silicene bilayers assuming AA and AB stacking in Figs. 38a and b are investigated by means of DFT-GGA+vdW [276]. The resulting averaged interlayer distances are 3.13 Å (AA) and 3.19 Å (AB). The AB Bernal stacking is energetically favorable by 34 meV/atom over the AA stacking (see also [279]) in agreement with findings for bilayer germanene [140] but in contrast to the graphene case, where the AA stacking is favored. The electronic KS band structures in DFT-GGA in Figs. 38c and d are distinctly different from that of the bilayer graphene in Fig. 37a, at least the band dispersions around the Dirac point at K and along the $K\Gamma$ and KM high-symmetry lines. Despite the fact that the 2D unit cell and the BZ are the same as in the monolayer case, only the number of atoms is doubled, while strongly modified lowest conduction and highest valence bands occur around the Fermi level. The AA stacking gives a zero-gap semiconductor, while the AB stacking results in a metal. The reason is the buckling of the silicene layers, the smaller interlayer distance, and the more extended p_z orbitals compared to the carbon case. In accordance to the electronic structure modifications the optical absorption in Figs. 38e and f exhibits practically no changes in the higher-energy region in the range of the $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions. However, in the lower-energy region of the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions drastic modi-

fications happen. Most interesting is the fact that the normalized spectrum $Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)/\sigma_0 \right]$ does not approach the value of 2 for $\omega \rightarrow 0$. Rather, the absorbance vanishes for AA stacking but increases for AB stacking. The peak related to the M_1 van Hove singularity in the monolayer case is drastically modified and shifted in opposite directions depending on the actual stacking.

The strong modifications of the bands near the Dirac point in Figs. 38c and d seem to vanish for increasing the distance of the silicene layers. The distance of the two silicene sheets is obviously increased in a heterostructure, where they are separated by a 2D insulator. Actually we study this effect for a silicene/ Al_2O_3 quadrilayer (see Fig. 39a) with the kagome geometry of Al_2O_3 as displayed in Fig. 12 [179]. Indeed, the band structure in Fig. 39b is similar to that of freestanding silicene in Fig. 16b, if the zone-folding aspect is taken into consideration. The band splittings due to the weak mutual interaction are very small. Consequently, in Fig. 39c the absorbance of the quadrilayer is nearly the same as twice the absorbance of freestanding silicene (see Fig. 35b) and so also twice of the silicene/ Al_2O_3 bilayer heterostructure.

4.3. Many-body effects

4.3.1. Excitonic insulator

The low-energy single-particle elementary excitations in undoped graphene are massless Dirac fermions. Because of the SOC-induced gap opening near K and K' the low-energy Dirac fermions possess a finite mass in freestanding silicene, germanene, and stanene [17]. The corresponding two-particle electron-hole pair excitations follow the single-particle trend (see e.g. Fig. 33). They determine the optical absorption spectra within the independent-(quasi)particle approximation as illustrated in Figs. 35a and 36a. Without SOC it holds

$Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(0) \right] = \sigma_0$ and $A(0) = \pi\alpha$ in the limit of small photon energies and in-plane light polarization. Including SOC, an absorption edge appears at the SOC-induced gap, at $\hbar\omega = E_g = 2\lambda_{SO}$. Including the screened Coulomb attraction between (quasi)electrons and (quasi)holes the formation of excitons, i.e., excitonic bound states below the absorption edge and dissociated excitons or even resonant excitons formed by (higher interband) transitions for photon energies above the gap, may be really or virtually excited.

In real 2D systems, embedded in an environment of upper and lower dielectrics with the 3D dielectric constants ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 (see Fig. 31), the statically screened electron-hole attraction in a Xene, Xane, or halogenated Xene sheet can be approximately described by the Rytova-Keldysh potential [280, 281]

$$W(\rho) = -\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{e^2}{\rho_0 \bar{\epsilon}} \left[H_0 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right) - N_0 \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right) \right] \quad (25)$$

with the in-plane distance of electron and hole ρ , the characteristic screening radius ρ_0 , and the average dielectric constant $\bar{\epsilon} = (\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)/2$ of the environment. The Struve and Neumann Bessel functions of second kind, H_0 and N_0 , respectively, appear. If the screening in the group-IV-derived sheet is investigated in the limit of vanishing sheet thickness $\delta \rightarrow 0$, expression (14) can be applied. It allows the definition of a static electronic sheet polarizability α_{2D} in length units, which is derived from the superlattice dielectric constant $\epsilon_{\parallel}^{SL}(0)$ (10) with $\epsilon_{\parallel}^{2D}(0) = 1 + 4\pi\alpha_{2D}/\delta$. The latter can be also computed using the independent-particle approximation and the KS electronic structure for a superlattice with vacuum and sheet in the unit cell [282]. Values resulting for Xenos (Xanes) are listed in Table 1 (Table 4). The sheet polarizability is related to the screening radius as $\rho_0 = 2\pi\alpha_{2D}/\bar{\epsilon}$.

In 3D semiconductors with finite gap E_g and a M_0 van Hove singular-

ity the electron-hole attraction leads to bound exciton states, which possess excitation energies E_{ex} below the independent-quasiparticle absorption edge E_g . The red shift $E_B = E_g - E_{\text{ex}}$ gives the binding energy of the electron-hole pair, the exciton [193]. This happens also in two dimensions [283, 284]. Thereby the attractive interaction can be approximately described by a potential similar to that in (25). The screening in 2D systems, in particular in freestanding ones with $\bar{\epsilon} = 1$, is ruled by the 2D polarizability $\alpha_{2\text{D}}$. Large binding energies E_B appear. In small gap systems, such as silicene, germanene, and stanene with small SOC-induced energy gap or even zero-gap systems, such as graphene, formally the exciton binding energy exceeds the band gap, $E_B > E_g$. First R. S. Knox noted that in this case a semiconductor should behave as an excitonic insulator (EI), where the valence electrons spontaneously occupy higher bands and form excitons [285]. The formation of the EI phase can be also interpreted as instability of the system against the formation of charge density waves (CDWs) or spin density waves (SDWs) [286, 287, 288]. A close formal similarity between the EI phase and the superconducting state has been predicted. However, physical properties of the two states of matter are different, for instance, no Meissner effect exists in an excitonic insulator.

Experimental evidence of EI phenomena in the 2D case has been found in TMDCs such as 1T-TiSe₂ [289]. In bilayer graphene embedded in hBN sheets and subject of strong external magnetic field at least features for exciton condensation could be observed [290, 291]. A variety of theoretical studies predicted that freestanding graphene is a possible candidate for the EI phase [292, 293, 294, 295, 296]. Experimental studies of this system showed

convincing evidence that it behaves as a semimetal, but not as an EI [297, 298]. Subsequent theoretical studies agree that graphene should not exhibit an EI phase [299, 300, 301].

The graphene-like buckled 2D allotropes of group-IV elements – silicene, germanene, and stanene – with small SOC-induced gaps and weak screening also ask the question concerning the existence of an EI phase [302]. A rigorous exploration of this question should be made in the framework of the *ab-initio* many-body theory [299]. Instead, a straightforward calculation of exciton binding energy E_B and fundamental gap E_g , perhaps modified by an external perturbation such as a vertical electric field U [303], should allow a reasonable discussion of the occurrence of the EI phase. According to (5) and without the Rashba SOC contribution the lowest electron-hole pair excitation energy near a K or K' point is given by

$$E(\boldsymbol{\kappa}) = 2\sqrt{\left(\frac{E_g}{2}\right)^2 + \hbar^2 v_F^2 \kappa^2} \approx E_g + \frac{\hbar^2 \kappa^2}{2\mu^*} \quad (26)$$

with a reduced effective mass $\mu^* = E_g/(2v_F)^2$ of the pair and a field-modified SOC-induced gap $E_g = E_g(U) = 2||U| - \lambda_{SO}|$ (6). The parabolic approximation (26) allows for a Wannier-Mott-like treatment of the band edge excitons [193]. The limit of small wavevectors κ in the parabolic expansion (26) corresponds to the limit $\rho \gg \rho_0$ in the attractive electron-hole potential $W(\rho)$ (25), which leads to the screened Coulomb potential of the 2D hydrogen model, $W(\rho) = -\frac{e^2}{\epsilon\rho}$. The exciton binding energy $E_B = E_B(U)$ amounts to [282]

$$E_B = 4\frac{\mu^*}{m} \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} R_H = \frac{2R_H}{\epsilon^2 m v_F^2} |\lambda_{SO} - |U|| \quad (27)$$

with hydrogen Rydberg $R_H = 13.605$ eV. With $E_g(U)$ (6) the ratio E_B/E_g is a constant versus the electric field. For freestanding biased Xenes with $\bar{\epsilon} = 1$ it only varies with v_F^2 . In the unbiased case $U = 0$ it holds $E_B/E_g = \frac{R_H}{\bar{\epsilon}^2 m v_F^2}$. With the HSE Fermi velocities from Table 1 the ratio values are 5.66, 6.23, and 7.91 for freestanding silicene, germanene, and stanene, respectively. All these values are larger than 1. Consequently, an EI phase should be possible independent of the strength of the external electric field, at least in the considered Wannier-Mott limit. Expression (27), however, suggests a strong influence of the dielectric environment of the Xene sheet. Embedding the Xenes by graphite-like BN with a dielectric constant of $\bar{\epsilon} = 4.89$, the ratio becomes smaller than 1, i.e., violating the EI phase. However, when the Xene sheets are placed on a SiO₂ substrate in vacuum, ratio values of about 1 may occur [302]. These estimates indicate that the occurrence of an EI phase is very sensitive to the dielectric environment of the studied 2D crystal.

If the formation of Wannier-Mott excitons near the band edge is considered with the electron-hole attraction described by the Rytova-Keldysh potential (25) and not by the 2D Coulomb potential, the exciton binding and its field dependence are modified. The calculated binding energies E_B are plotted in units of the band gap E_g versus the bias field in Fig. 40. Thereby, the buckling parameters Δ , which are similar as those in Table 1, are taken from [304]. In the fieldfree case $U = 0$ one finds $E_B = 10$ (Si), 106 (Ge), and 170 (Sn) meV [302]. Comparing with the HSE SOC-induced gaps in Table 1, it still holds $E_B/E_g > 1$, which could be an indicator for the EI phase. The ratios in Fig. 40 are however field-dependent, in contrast to the 2D hydrogen limit. They almost monotonically decrease with rising

field strength. Above critical values of $U/\Delta = 0.55$ (Si), 0.25 (Ge), and 0.08 (Sn) eV/Å the possibility of an EI phase vanishes. The corresponding bias values are above the critical value $|U| = \lambda_{SO}$ [217, 226] for the field-induced transition from a TI into a trivial insulator. In any case, a field-induced excitonic insulator-semiconductor phase transition is displayed in Fig. 40. The observation appears to be enough evidence of the EI phase in freestanding Xenes to warrant further studies, especially experimental ones. However, first the preparation of such 2D systems in sufficient quality has to be managed.

4.3.2. Saddle-point and resonant excitons

Despite the discussion in Sec. 4.3.1 of a possible EI phase with features in the energy range of the fundamental gap of (field-modified) Xenes, experimental studies of graphene measure an optical conductivity in the near infrared and visible spectral range close to the value $\sigma_0 = e^2/4\hbar$ [6, 7], a result which can be easily understood in the independent-(quasi)particle picture as shown in (19). However, optical spectra of graphene in the ultraviolet region ask for overcoming the independent-(quasi)particle approach as illustrated by the strong influence of the used XC approximation evinced by the comparison of Figs. 32a and 35b. This holds especially for the van Hove feature at 4.62 eV of graphene supported by an insulator. The pronounced peak goes back to a saddle point in the interband electronic structure at the M point of the BZ as illustrated in Fig. 33. Comparing with experimental spectra, both the position and the shape of this feature reveal the role of quasiparticle and excitonic effects [201, 203, 253, 254, 276, 278, 305]. Instead of independent interband transitions, excitonic interactions give rise to resonances of correlated electron-hole pairs, which however do not include bound states, if the

kinetic energy of the electron-hole pair is negative at this saddle-point van Hove singularity. Nevertheless, the red shift of the peak due to the excitonic effects nearly tends to compensate the blue shift due to QP effects treated within GW approximation [201, 203, 276].

Similar many-body effects appear in the optical spectra of the other group-IV honeycomb systems, e.g. silicene [276]. This is illustrated in Fig. 41 for the in-plane optical conductivity. The low-energy region $\hbar\omega < 0.5$ eV is not shown in Fig. 41 for technical and scientific reasons discussed above. Because of the Dirac cones, the calculation of optical spectra requires an extremely dense \mathbf{k} -point sampling around the corner points K and K'. Moreover, the direct diagonalization of the homogeneous BSE (12) may lead to negative electron-hole pairs eigenvalues (see discussion of the EI in Sec. 4.2.1). Nevertheless, the absorption spectrum $Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] / \sigma_0$ ($\omega \rightarrow 0$) tends to 1 for small frequencies. The DFT spectrum in Fig. 41a exhibits pronounced peaks near 1.6 and 3.9 eV. They are substantially shifted toward higher energies by the QP effects of about 0.5 and 0.8 eV, respectively. Including excitonic effects, within the GW-BSE approach, the IPA spectrum is roughly recovered with a minor spectral redistribution. The imaginary part in Fig. 41b tends to vanish for $\omega \rightarrow 0$ in agreement with the model result (24). Interestingly, the peak positions in $Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right]$ agree with energy zeros in the imaginary part $Im \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega) \right] = 0$.

The first peak in Fig. 41a is again due to a saddle-point van Hove singularity at M. Its physical background is the same as discussed above for the saddle-point excitons in graphene, of course, at higher energies, but with a similar asymmetric Fano lineshape, and still a significant $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ character.

The van Hove singularity is clearly visible in the interband band structure and JDOS in Fig. 33. The higher energy peak is due to the combination of excitons related to $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions. Several minima M_0 van Hove singularities due to several interband transitions along the ΓM direction (see Fig. 33 for silicene) contribute. The spectral feature at the high-energy side slightly below 4 eV (DFT-GGA, G_0W_0 -BSE) or 5 eV (G_0W_0) may be traced back to an M_0 critical point at K (see Fig. 33, middle panel). The excitonic effects move the blueshifted quasiparticle peak nearly back to the DFT position. The stronger redshift compared to the case of the saddle-point peak can be traced back to the formation of bound excitons. However, the exciton binding energies are small because of the extremely small interband masses visible from the interband dispersion in Fig. 33. Moreover, exciton bound states of higher transitions and scattering states of lower transitions overlap in the energy region of this peak. These bound excitons are, therefore, resonant with dissociated electron-hole pair states, belonging to lower van Hove singularities, and may be called resonant excitons.

The influence of a substrate on electronic properties of Xenes have been discussed in Sec. 3.3. Figure 39c for silicene/ Al_2O_3 stacks shows that substrates, which give rise only to a vdW interaction with the Xene overlayer, have a minor influence on the optical absorption. In the case of hybridization across the interface, as e.g. 3×3 silicene on 4×4 Ag(111), the substrate effect should be more important. This is illustrated in Fig. 42, where the optical absorption of freestanding silicene is compared with those of the silicene, which is “peeled off” from the silver substrate. The calculations are performed within the independent-particle approximation according to the

found tendency of cancellation of excitonic and quasiparticle effects in Fig. 41. The “peeled-off” silicene conserves the atomic arrangement of the Si atoms in the silicene overlayer of Ag(111). Its absorption spectrum shows a gap of the order of 0.3 eV [112, 116, 255] due to the symmetry lowering. Its overall lineshape agrees among the DFT-GGA descriptions [261, 276].

The absorption spectrum in Fig. 42 demonstrates that the two main peaks of the freestanding silicene are almost conserved in the spectrum of the peeled-off Si layer. Of course, the peaks are broadened and reduced in intensity. This is expected for the higher-energy peak around 4 eV because of the dominance of $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transitions. A remnant of the saddle-point peak near 1.6 eV is also still visible. However, quite dramatic modifications appear in the low-frequency region. An absorption edge near 0.3 eV and a new peak near 1 eV appear, because of the absence of the Dirac cones near the K and K' points. The inset in Fig. 42 makes obvious the disappearance of the plateau $Re \left[\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega \rightarrow 0) \right] = \frac{e^2}{4\hbar}$ or $A(\omega \rightarrow 0) = \pi\alpha$ [267, 268], which is discussed in Sec. 4.2.2. Figure 42 illustrates how optical spectra yield fingerprints for the presence or destruction of Dirac cones due to the different arrangements of group-IV atoms in a honeycomb geometry. In a real spectrum of 3×3 silicene on Ag(111) [306] the absorption spectrum will be substantially changed by the silver substrate with a reflectivity close to 100 % in the infrared region, which remains practically uninfluenced in the presence of the Si overlayer [307].

4.3.3. Band edge excitons

In order to find strongly bound exciton states below the independent-quasiparticle absorption edge, 2D group-IV crystals with reasonable energy

gaps have to be investigated. Such systems may be prepared by hydrogenation or halogenation of honeycomb group-IV arrangements. The experimental spectrum of germanane (GeH), synthesized via a topochemical deintercalation of CaGe_2 layered material [98], is displayed in Fig. 43. The underlying silver-black material has a broad absorption over the visible spectral range, which is moved into the infrared region with increasing temperature. The linear approximation used to determine the absorption edge in Fig. 43a suggests an optical band gap of approximately 1.59 eV. The disappearance of sharp exciton peaks and the huge temperature-induced red shift indicate that the platelet samples are far from ideal 2D crystals with alternating arrangement of the hydrogen atoms (see Fig. 6). Size and disorder effects, including remaining Ge-Cl bonds, lead to spectral broadenings, so that isolated bound exciton peaks are not visible. Only an edge, whose position can be identified in Fig. 43a with the low-temperature optical gap, allows for a gap measurement. Higher temperatures $T = 300 - 525\text{K}$ well below the dehydrogenation temperature give strong temperature-induced redshifts toward an optical gap of about 0.4 eV. They also suggest a coupling to the lattice vibrations.

Calculated absorption spectra for photon energies below the fundamental (direct) QP gap based on GW on top of KS eigenvalues within PBE are displayed in Fig. 44a. The gap values of the chair-like configuration are 5.4 (graphane), 3.6 (silicane), and 2.4 (germanane) eV from Table 4 [91]. For graphane the value is identical with other computations [23, 92, 95] but not with all [204]. Variations in the results of the G_0W_0 calculations are observable with $E_g = 3.8/4.1$ (silicane) and $3.5/2.4$ (germanane) eV [88, 89, 94]. The approximate HSE values are even somewhat larger with 4.0

and 3.6 eV [88]. For stanane a G_0W_0 gap of 1.63 eV is predicted [93]. Below the independent-QP absorption edge Fig. 44a shows series of bound excitons with sizeable (at least for silicane and germanane) oscillator strengths. Their positions do not follow the simple Rydberg series formula of a 2D hydrogen atom. The deviation follows from the character of the Rytova-Keldysh potential (25) deviating from the weakly bound limit of $W(\rho) = -e^2/\rho$ with energy eigenvalues $E_n = \frac{-1}{(n-\frac{1}{2})^2} R_H \frac{\mu^*}{m}$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$ and μ^* - effective interband mass). In addition, the diagonalization of the two-particle Hamiltonian (13) gives excitons built mainly by higher interband transitions near Γ , here into higher conduction bands (see Fig. 20). Since the influence of SOC is neglected in the calculation of Fig. 44 [91] the uppermost valence band at Γ is twofold degenerate, while the lowest conduction band is not.

Most interesting are the first bound exciton peaks at $\hbar\omega = 3.6$ eV (graphane), 2.7 eV (silicane), and 1.8 eV (germanane) in the in-plane spectra in the left panels of Fig. 44a, where SOC is not taken into account. In the case of stanane [93], the situation in Fig. 45 is different. The strong SOC leads to a splitting of the first exciton peak near 1.75 eV into two at 1.54 and 1.86 eV, reflecting the SOC-induced splitting of the upper valence bands. With respect to the GW QP gaps in Table 4 huge exciton binding energies of $E_B = 1.8$ (CH), 0.9 (SiH), 0.6 (GeH), and 0.3 (SnH) eV are derived from the *ab initio* studies. They are in reasonable agreement with other calculated values $E_B = 1.6$ eV (CH) [94, 95], 1.07 eV (SiH) [94, 229], and 0.92 eV (GeH) [94, 229]. The trend of E_B along the row C \rightarrow Sn is monotonous as a consequence of the decreasing \mathbf{k} -dispersion of the bands forming the gap near Γ (see Fig. 20) as well as the increasing electronic polarizability α_{2D} of

the sheets, $\alpha_{2D} = 1.1$ (CH), 3.1 (SiH), and 3.5 (GeH) Å (see Table 4). These values are much smaller than the polarizabilities of the small-gap Xenon, e.g. $\alpha_{2D} = 76.2$ Å of silicene (see Table 1). The exciton binding in Fig. 44a directly correlates with the extent of the two-particle electron-hole pair wave function in Fig. 44b. Assuming that the hole is strongly localized in a σ -bond orbital between two group-IV atoms, the probability to find an electron characterizes the localization character of an exciton. A clear chemical trend is visible. The computed wave functions allow the evaluation of an (in-plane) exciton localization radius $r_{\text{ex}} = 5.8$ (CH), 9.7 (SiH), and 16.0 (GeH) Å, i.e., a measure of the average distance between electron and hole [91]. While the lowest electron-hole-pair excitation in germanane tends to be a 2D Wannier-Mott exciton, the lowest-energy exciton in graphane shows more a Frenkel-like character.

The probability to find an electron in Fig. 44b for graphane is a consequence of the single-particle wave function in Fig. 21b. The lowest conduction-band Bloch function at Γ reflects its C-H antibonding character with the electron mainly localized on top of the H atoms. In contrast, the hole is localized in C-C bonds. The creation of such a lowest-energy exciton is accompanied by a charge transfer from the carbon plane into regions outside the graphane sheet on top of the hydrogens (see Fig. 21). The vanishing overlap of the electron and hole wave functions in such an exciton strongly reduces the associated oscillator strength. Although the optical matrix element at Γ is not zero according to the group theory, the lowest interband transitions are practically dipole-forbidden. Consequently, in Fig. 44a the graphane spectrum has been enhanced by a factor 600 to reach seemingly similar absorption

strengths as for silicane and germanane. In the SiH and GeH cases the contributing band states have a strong wave function overlap (see Fig. 44b) and dipole-allowed optical transitions with significant intraatomic contributions. As a consequence graphane, on one side, and silicane or germanane, on the other side, may have different optoelectronic applications. The almost vanishing dipole matrix elements together with the huge exciton binding suggest graphane to be an ideal material for a possible observation of Bose-Einstein condensation by continuous optical pumping [95]. In silicane and germanane the giant near-band edge oscillator strengths give rise to extremely short radiative lifetimes preventing condensation. The strong light-matter coupling together with the strong exciton binding makes them to promising candidates for active optoelectronic devices [91].

Within the effective-mass approximation with reduced interband masses $\mu^* = 0.28$ (CH), 0.09 (SiH), and 0.05 (GeH) m from Table 4, the 2D exciton problem with the screened potential $W(\rho)$ (25) can be analytically solved applying a variational approach with a $1s$ exciton trial wave function [282]. With the *ab initio* computed values for μ^* and α_{2D} the exciton binding is excellently described. This is illustrated in Fig. 46, where the exciton binding energy is plotted versus the 2D insulator with honeycomb symmetry, taken from *ab initio* calculations and the variational approach with effective masses and polarizabilities from Table 4. Besides graphane, silicane, and germanane also the hydrogenated SiC sheet as well 2D nitrides with a graphene-like atomic lattice are displayed [308].

An alternative route to tune the electronic and optical properties is a halogenation of group-IV sheets instead of hydrogenation. In the limit of fully

functionalized sheets the hydrogen atoms of Xanes are replaced by halogens. A prototypical example is fully fluorinated graphene, i.e., fluorographene (CF). In the chair conformation fluorine atoms are alternating on both sides of the group-IV basal plane. The electronic structure of fluorographene is investigated in Sec. 2.2.2. Direct gaps are opened at the Γ point in the BZ with KS values of 3.1 eV in DFT-GGA [82] and 2.75 eV also in DFT-LDA [309]. The QP corrections within GW significantly open the quasiparticle gaps to values of 7.5 eV [82] and 7.01 eV [309], i.e., to much larger values compared to graphane with 5.4 eV. The excitonic effects significantly modify the independent-QP spectrum (see Fig. 47a). A drastic redistribution of spectral strength toward lower energies happens. A bound exciton peak occurs at $\hbar\omega = 5.05$ eV [309], indicating a red shift, i.e., an exciton binding energy, of 1.96 eV between QP and optical gap. For comparison, an experimental spectrum of fluorographene is displayed in Fig. 47b. Because of disorder effects no bound exciton state is observed. On the other hand, the optical gap is determined to be about 3 eV [79], much below the theoretical one of about 5 eV. Besides disorder, also optical effects of the three-layer system CF/SiO₂/Si substrate may have an influence on the gap determination from optical spectra [see formula (16)].

5. Topological quantities

5.1. Topological insulator

5.1.1. Phenomenological characterization

Around the turn of the 21st century, classes of new materials exhibiting novel quantum mechanical phenomena have been discovered or rediscovered.

Among them are topological insulators, Weyl and Dirac semimetals, and several topological crystalline phases, e.g. mirror Chern insulators. In a phenomenological manner a TI is a material that is insulating in its interior but electrically conductive on its surface [310]. In the bulk gap ungapped surface states appear, which are symmetry-protected, for instance, they do not disappear by surface passivation, for instance, by atom adsorption at the surface, and, in principle, should not depend on the surface orientation. Moreover, in the case of 3D crystals the corresponding surface bands should be linear at the crossing point, the Dirac point, in the gap and exhibit spin polarization. The bulk gap itself may be inverted. For instance, in an *sp*-bonded system *p*-related band states appear at energies higher than the *s*-band states. The 3D zincblende HgTe and diamond-structure α -tin crystals are instructive examples for such a band inversion [311].

The appearance of symmetry-protected gapless states, which are robust against perturbations and manifested at boundaries, is in accordance with the so-called bulk-boundary correspondence principle [312]. The corresponding insulators are more precisely called first-order TIs. Nontrivial materials that apparently violate the bulk-boundary correspondence are referred as higher-order TIs [313, 314]. Obviously, all these phenomena are related to the topology of the electronic bands, i.e., the crystal symmetry and the relativistic effects, especially the SOC. Indeed, band symmetry is the key to discuss topological properties. Applying the method of symmetry indicators to suitable 3D nonmagnetic compounds allows to highlight huge numbers of TIs, topological crystalline insulators, and topological semimetals [315].

In two dimensions a time-reversal (TR) invariant TI can be also identified

by robust helical edge modes appearing in its bulk gap. Corresponding sheet materials are also known as a QSH insulators, i.e., 2D insulators which show a QSH phase [214, 215, 310, 316]. In a nanoribbon, made by a 2D TI, the QSH state supports a pair of counter-propagating spin-polarized edge modes within the gap. A quantum Hall response in such a TR-protected system is physically realized due to SOC. At the boundary of the quantum liquid a dissipationless spin current $j_i^k = \sum_k \sigma_{ij}^k F_j$ appears driven by an electric field F_j . The response is mediated by the spin Hall conductivity, σ_{ij}^k , a response function, which represents a third-rank tensor with the Cartesian orientation i of the spin current and k of the spin component [239]. Dissipationless quantum spin currents at room temperature have been predicted [317] for semiconductor quantum wells, e.g. HgTe/CdHgTe ones, which are found to be 2D TIs for HgTe wells thicker than a critical thickness of 6.3 nm, whereas thinner quantum wells should be ordinary insulators [318, 319]. Similar to HgTe quantum wells [319], an observation of the QSH effect up to 100 K in a true monolayer WTe₂ crystal has been reported [320].

5.1.2. Example: Iodinated germanene

The bonding geometry of a halogenated honeycomb germanene sheet is displayed in Fig. 6. Because of the interest in the band topology, we focus on the heaviest halogen element, the iodine I, with an enhanced SOC. According to Table 3 the topology of GeI hardly depends on the treatment of XC. It is therefore sufficient to investigate its band structure in DFT-PBE quality. In addition to the general band structure in Fig. 24a, it is shown in Fig. 48a versus the hexagonal BZ (see Fig. 2c) in a more narrow energy range around the chemical potential of the electrons in a midgap position. The lowest

conduction band and the three highest valence bands are depicted around the Γ point. The highest valence band shows a Mexican-hat-like dispersion. The inverted parabola near Γ and the flat conduction band represent the $s - p$ inversion due to SOC but also scalar-relativistic effects. The parities of these bands at Γ are interchanged with respect to the pure germanene in Fig. 16. According to Fig. 48a the GeI sheet is a TI with an indirect gap $\Gamma K \rightarrow \Gamma$ of 0.31 eV and a larger direct $\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$ gap of 0.40 eV [321].

In order to discuss topological edge states zigzag (see Fig. 9) GeI nanoribbons are suitable model systems. The dangling bonds of the Ge edge atoms are passivated by hydrogens to avoid chemical edge states. The bonding and antibonding states of the Ge-H bond yield levels far away from the center of the GeI gap and, therefore, are not visible in Fig. 48c. The atomic geometry of a resulting edge is illustrated in Fig. 48b. Because of the quantum size effect the fundamental gap of the ribbon depends on its width proportional to the number N of non-primitive rectangular unit cells between the edges. According to Fig. 9b they can be constructed by multiples of non-primitive rectangular unit cells with four Ge and four I atoms. For the applied $N = 16$ the quantum size effect is negligible [226]. The resulting band structure in Fig. 48c exhibits the 2D GeI gap within the folded 2D bands but almost linear 1D bands of chiral topological edge states in the fundamental gap with a Dirac point near the chemical potential of the undoped ribbon material.

In the case of pure germanene nanoribbons the band linearity is more or less destroyed, because of the insufficiently strong SOC [226]. The topological gap states are spin polarized with spin orientation perpendicular to the ribbon edge. The angle of spin with the ribbon plane is difficult to deter-

mine, since the DFT total energy only weakly varies with this angle. The topological states are localized at the edges but decay exponentially toward the ribbon center (see Fig. 48d for pure germanene). Therefore, for sufficiently thick ribbons the existence of a QSH phase is predicted, as here for germanene. In too small ribbons the edge states may form “bonding” and “antibonding” combinations and, consequently, open a gap and destroy the 1D linear bands.

5.2. Topological invariants

5.2.1. With inversion symmetry

A Z_2 topological invariant has been proposed by Kane and Mele to classify the TR-invariant band insulators in two dimensions [214, 215]. The Z_2 value characterizes, whether a 2D system is topologically trivial, $Z_2 = 0$, or nontrivial, $Z_2 = 1$. For TR-invariant band insulators with extra (spatial) inversion symmetry the Z_2 invariant can be easily computed using the formalism of Fu and Kane [322]. They introduce a matrix $\hat{\omega}(\mathbf{k})$ of matrix elements of the TR-symmetry operator with Bloch factors of occupied bands. In centrosymmetric systems the determinant of this antisymmetric matrix is its Pfaffian $Pf[\hat{\omega}(\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}})]$, which is equal to $\sqrt{\det[\hat{\omega}(\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}})]}$, excepting the sign.

In TR-invariant systems, Xenes, Xanes, and halogenated Xenes, there are special \mathbf{k} -points, \mathbf{k}_{TRIM} , in the BZ, which are TR invariant and satisfy the equation $-\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}} = \mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}} + \mathbf{G}$ for a reciprocal lattice vector \mathbf{G} . There are four such TR invariant moment (TRIM) points in the 2D BZ. They are illustrated for hexagonal Bravais lattices in Fig. 49a. Since an M point and its corresponding opposite point on the BZ boundary are separated by a reciprocal lattice vector $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{b}_1$ or \mathbf{b}_2 , besides the Γ point, in total, three

equivalent M points represent TRIM points. The change in the TR polarization associated with a cylinder oriented along \mathbf{G} can be calculated in analogy to the calculations of the charge polarization in a Berry phase [323, 324]. The result can be expressed in terms of the real phase factor [325]

$$\delta_{\text{TRIM}} = \frac{\sqrt{\det [\hat{\omega}(\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}})]}}{\text{Pf} [\hat{\omega}(\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}})]} = \pm 1. \quad (28)$$

In two dimensions the single Z_2 invariant is given by the exponent ν related to the sum over all TRIM points

$$(-1)^\nu = \prod_{j=1}^4 \delta_{\text{TRIM}_j}. \quad (29)$$

In the centrosymmetric systems the calculation of (28) can be traced back to

$$\delta_{\text{TRIM}} = \prod_{m=1}^N \zeta_{2m}(\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}}) \quad (30)$$

with $\zeta_{2m}(\mathbf{k}_{\text{TRIM}}) = \pm 1$ as the parity eigenvalue of the $2m$ th occupied band at \mathbf{k}_{TRIM} , which shares the same eigenvalue $\zeta_{2m} = \zeta_{2m-1}$ with its Kramers degenerate partner. N is the number of twofold-degenerate valence bands. In (29) $\nu = 1$ (an odd number in general) corresponds to $(-1)^\nu = -1$ and $\nu = 0$ (an even number modulo 2) to $(-1)^\nu = 1$ with $Z_2 = 1$ and $Z_2 = 0$, respectively. As an example the occupied bands of germanene together with the parities of the occupied Kramers degenerate states at the TRIM points are displayed in Fig. 49b. The quantities (30) are $\delta_\Gamma = (1)^3(-1)^1 = -1$ and $\delta_M = (1)^2(-1)^2 = 1$, resulting in $(-1)^\nu = -1$. One concludes $Z_2 = 1$, i.e., germanene is a TI, which should show the QSH phase.

The influence of chemical functionalization of germanene by iodine and hydrogen is described in Fig. 50 displaying the band structures computed

using the HSE hybrid functional and the parities of occupied states at TRIM points [239]. The most drastic influence of the functionalization on the bands appears at the K and K' points which, however, are not TRIM points, where huge gaps of the order of about 4 eV (GeI) and 7 eV (GeH) are opened. Gaps appear near Γ with 0.43 eV (GeI, direct $\Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma$) and 1.52 eV (GeH), while the interband distance at Γ is 1.45 eV for germanene. The number of occupied Kramers degenerate bands increases from $N = 4$ (germanene) to $N = 11$ (GeI) or $N = 5$ (GeH). The three Ge-derived 2D crystals lead to a phase factor (30) -1 at Γ , independent of the number of occupied bands. The corresponding value at M is $+1$ (GeI, Ge) or -1 (GeH). Consequently, an odd value, $\nu = 1$, appears for GeI and Ge, while an even value of ν is calculated for germanene. The pure and iodinated germanene are TIs ($Z_2 = 1$), whereas germanene is a trivial system or normal insulator ($Z_2 = 0$). There is agreement in literature concerning these conclusions [61, 87, 93, 239, 320]. For other functionalized germanene sheets the Z_2 values are listed in Table 3. Of course, also silicene and stanene are TIs, independent of the chosen XC functional. Different characterizations can be found for plumbene in literature. The reasons why plumbene should be a trivial insulator [72, 222], a TI [71] or a spin Chern insulator are described within many-band TB Hamiltonians [326].

5.2.2. Without inversion symmetry

If the Xene, Xane, and halogenated Xene systems are perturbed by vertical electric fields [87, 93, 226, 227] or brought in contact with substrates [164, 166] the (spatial) inversion symmetry is broken. The symmetry is reduced, in the case of the Xenos to the subgroup C_{3v} of D_{3d} . The Kramers

degeneracy of the bands is lifted and the parity is not a good quantum number. The Fu-Kane parity method (29) cannot anymore be applied. The determinant and the Pfaffian of the Bloch matrix of the TR-symmetry operator $\hat{\omega}(\mathbf{k})$ have to be directly calculated, at least for the entirety of TRIM points. Thereby, in principle, one has to fix the gauge of the Bloch wave functions on one half of the BZ [322, 325]. In praxis, using an electronic structure code, e.g. such described in [37, 38, 39, 40], this is impossible since the KS equation is independently solved for a given \mathbf{k} point. An arbitrary \mathbf{k} -dependent phase may occur, which violates a fixed relation between the wave function phases at different points in the BZ. This gauge problem already appears calculating Wannier functions from Bloch functions.

To handle the gauge-fixing problem the computation of the Z_2 topological invariant of a band or topological insulator is based on the non-Abelian Berry connection [325]. For 2D materials a gauge corresponding to hybrid Wannier functions that are maximally localized in one dimension [327] is used. According to the Fu-Kane theory, the number of Kramers pair switchings modulo 2 along a line connecting two TRIM points defines the topological invariant of the system [322, 325]. The Kramers pair switching is equivalent to the “partner switchings” of the Wannier charge centers (WCCs) during a closed (Wilson) loop in the BZ. The evolution of the WCCs can be related to the phase $\theta(\mathbf{k})$ of the eigenvalues of the position operator projected onto the occupied band states [327, 328]. The methods of Yu et al. [327] or Soluyanov et al. [328] have been implemented in the VASP code [329] and the Z2pack [330], respectively.

As examples, the WCC evolutions, the evolution of the phase $\theta(\mathbf{k})$ along

the connection line ΓM (in units of $2\pi/a$), are plotted in Figs. 51 and 52 for field-modified germanene, iodinated germanene, and stanene on a H-passivated 4H-SiC(001) substrate [166]. The phases in Fig. 51 for biased germanene show a completely different behavior for electric-field strengths just below or above the critical field strength F_z^{crit} . The topological phase transition TI \rightarrow trivial insulator is obvious. The Z_2 jumps from $Z_2 = 1$ to $Z_2 = 0$ at $F_z = F_z^{\text{crit}}$.

In Fig. 52 the WCC phase evolutions are represented for stanene on a supporting H-passivated SiC substrate in comparison to freestanding iodinated germanene. Each occupied band gives one phase, which however can be degenerate. The partner switching is clearly visible. It guarantees that a chosen horizontal line has an odd number of crossings with the phase curves. As a consequence, not only freestanding GeI but also supported stanene is a TI. Most important, the TI character is conserved for stanene on the substrate. However, the interpretation of Fig. 52a is difficult because of many occupied bands. This is a general problem in applying the WCC evolution method for systems with too many atoms in the atomic basis. Systems as GeI in Fig. 52b with four atoms and 22 valence electrons in the unit cell, however, can be relatively easily interpreted.

5.3. Spin Hall conductivity

5.3.1. Frequency dependence

The topological character of a material depends on the strength of SOC. Therefore, an interesting observable for the 2D systems Xenes, Xanes, and halogenated Xenes is the spin Hall conductivity, which vanishes for vanishing SOC, i.e., the internal SOC-related pseudomagnetic field. Intrinsic spin Hall

effects are relativistic spin-orbit coupling phenomena in which an electrical current can generate transverse spin currents and vice versa [331]. Such a situation is schematically depicted in Fig. 53, where an electric field in y -direction induces a corresponding electrical current. The effective magnetic field of the SOC generates a transverse movement of the electrons with a sign according to their spin orientation. Consequently, a vertical but in-plane spin current appears. The spin Hall conductivity mediates the effect of the electric field on spin. It can be described by a Kubo formula similar to that combining (15) with (10). The Hall configuration in Fig. 53 suggests to identify the velocity of the electrons in the electrical current by $v_j = v_y = \frac{1}{m}p_y$. The velocity of the spins in the transverse spin current becomes $v_i \rightarrow v_x^{\text{spin},z} = \frac{1}{2i} [\hat{\sigma}_z, v_y]_+$. The spin component chosen in z -direction is a consequence of the hexagonal symmetry, which guarantees that only the component $\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega)$ of the third-rank tensor (intrinsic) spin Hall conductivity is nonzero [332]. The space group of the buckled monolayers, $P\bar{3}m1$, corresponds to the magnetic Laue group $\bar{3}m11'$. The third-rank tensor σ_{ij}^k only possesses four independent tensor components, among them $\sigma_{xy}^z = -\sigma_{yx}^z$ dominates.

In analogy to the Kubo formula in (10) one finds in independent-(quasi)particle approximation [239, 321, 332, 333]

$$\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega) = \frac{ie^2}{\omega A} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\nu, \nu'} w(\mathbf{k}) [f(\varepsilon_\nu(\mathbf{k})) - f(\varepsilon_{\nu'}(\mathbf{k}))] \frac{\langle \nu \mathbf{k} | v_x^{\text{spin},z} | \nu' \mathbf{k} \rangle \langle \nu' \mathbf{k} | v_y | \nu \mathbf{k} \rangle}{\varepsilon_\nu(\mathbf{k}) - \varepsilon_{\nu'}(\mathbf{k}) + \hbar\omega + i\eta}. \quad (31)$$

Its strong relationship to the band topology is obvious after rewriting it into

$$\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega) = e^2 \hbar \frac{1}{A} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\nu} w(\mathbf{k}) f(\varepsilon_\nu(\mathbf{k})) \Omega_\nu^z(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \quad (32)$$

with the dynamic spin Berry phase connection of an occupied Bloch-Pauli state $|\nu\mathbf{k}\rangle$ [332, 334, 335, 336]

$$\Omega_\nu^z(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = \sum_{\nu'} \frac{(-2)Im \{ \langle \nu\mathbf{k} | \frac{1}{2} [\hat{\sigma}_z, v_y]_+ | \nu'\mathbf{k} \rangle \langle \nu'\mathbf{k} | v_y | \nu\mathbf{k} \rangle \}}{[\varepsilon_\nu(\mathbf{k}) - \varepsilon_{\nu'}(\mathbf{k})]^2 - (\hbar\omega + i\eta)^2}. \quad (33)$$

The convergence of $\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega)$ depends on the size of the fundamental gap and the strength of the SOC. It requires a high density of the \mathbf{k} -point sampling, in particular in BZ regions where the Bloch states are substantially influenced by SOC. Therefore, a self-adapting BZ integration scheme [337] is applied in some cases [87, 321]. Other approaches use an interpolation scheme based on maximally localized Wannier functions [336, 338].

Frequency-dependent spin Hall conductivities $\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega)$, which are computed with electronic states from an *ab initio* DFT-PBE scheme for the chemical potential in a midgap position and low temperatures [239], are displayed in Fig. 54. Characteristic spectral features appear in the real parts as well as imaginary parts due to van Hove singularities in the interband band structure $\Delta\varepsilon_{cv}(\mathbf{k})$, for instance, at high-symmetry points in Fig. 33, or bands structures in Figs. 24a and 20. The first pronounced spectral structures appear at the direct fundamental gaps in DFT-PBE at 0.40 eV for GeI, 0.02 eV for Ge, and 0.87 eV for GeH. However, also higher-energy critical points are visible in the spectra of iodinated and hydrogenated germanene. For instance, additional structures appear near 1.1 eV and in the interval 3.0 – 3.5 eV in the GeI spectra. The structures near 1.1 eV are dominated by interband transitions near the M points. The higher-energy features are due to interband transitions near K or K' points. The peak heights vary with the broadening parameter η . The spectra seem to be composed by Lorentzians or

their derivations. Characteristic differences appear in the low-frequency limit $\omega \rightarrow 0$. While the imaginary parts vanish in this limit, the real parts of the spin Hall conductivity approach either values close to $\sigma_{xy}^z(0) = 3.87 \times 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1}$ (GeI, Ge), i.e., the value of the reciprocal von Klitzing constant, or tend to zero, $\sigma_{xy}^z(0) = 0$, (GeH). In units of $e^2/h = 1/(25812.8\Omega)$ one seemingly observes $\sigma_{xy}^z(0) = N \frac{e^2}{h}$ with $N = 1$ (GeI, Ge) or $N = 0$ (GeH), at least for vanishing broadening η . In the framework of the reached numerical accuracy one may conclude that the topological insulators iodinated and pure germanene with $Z_2 = 1$ give rise to a quantization of the static spin Hall conductivity, while the trivial insulator germanane with $Z_2 = 0$ tends to a vanishing quantity.

5.3.2. Quantization

The above findings seem to be in agreement with the simple tight-binding model, proposed by Kane and Mele in a seminal paper [215], which realizes the quantum spin Hall effect (QSHE). To study further this effect the electronic-structure model (4) for low-energy excitations near the K or K' points in the hexagonal BZ of Xenon, graphene, silicene, germanene, and stanene, is applied. In addition to the two different SOC contributions proportional to λ_{SO} and λ_R , respectively, in (4), the influence of a vertical electric field (see Fig. 17a), described by the bias voltage U , is studied. Similarly to the calculation of the optical conductivity in (20), the spin Hall conductivity

with spin component in z -direction (31) can be formulated as [87, 219, 239]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xy}^z(\omega) = & \frac{ie^2}{\omega} \sum_{\zeta=+,-} \int \frac{d^2\boldsymbol{\kappa}}{(2\pi)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d\varepsilon}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{d\varepsilon'}{2\pi} \frac{f(\varepsilon) - f(\varepsilon')}{\varepsilon - \varepsilon' + \hbar\omega + i\eta} \times \\ & \times \text{Tr} \left\{ \left[\hat{V}_x^z(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon') \right] \left[\hat{V}_y(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \hat{A}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \varepsilon) \right] \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where the velocity matrix $\hat{V}_i(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa})$ (21) in (20) is replaced by the velocity of the spin component in z -direction $\hat{V}_x^z(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa})$ and $i = x$ and $j = y$ are fixed according to the Hall configuration (see Fig. 53). The spin velocity is given by

$$\hat{V}_x^z(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) = \frac{1}{2\hbar} \left[\hat{S}_z, \hat{V}_y(\zeta, \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \right]_+ \quad (35)$$

with the z -component \hat{S}_z of the spin operator in the four-orbital spinor basis.

The application of the spectral functions (7), the carrier velocity (21), and the spin velocity (35) yields for vanishing temperature and zero external electric field $U = 0$ [87]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re} [\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega)] &= -\frac{e^2}{h} \frac{1}{1 + (a\lambda_R/\hbar v_F)^2} \frac{\lambda_{SO}}{\hbar|\omega|} \ell n \frac{|2\text{max} - \hbar|\omega|}{2\text{max} + \hbar|\omega|}, \\ \text{Im} [\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega)] &= \frac{e^2}{h} \pi \frac{1}{1 + (a\lambda_R/\hbar v_F)^2} \frac{\lambda_{SO}}{\hbar\omega} \Theta(\hbar|\omega| - 2\text{max}) \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

with $\text{max} = \max(|\mu|, \lambda_{SO})$. In the static limit $\omega \rightarrow 0$ one finds [87, 219]

$$\text{Re} [\sigma_{xy}^z(0)] = \frac{e^2}{h} \frac{1}{1 + (a\lambda_R/\hbar v_F)^2} \frac{\lambda_{SO}}{\text{max}}. \quad (37)$$

One can conclude that even for the Fermi level in the fundamental gap of the Xenex, $\lambda_{SO} > |\mu|$ and $\frac{\lambda_{SO}}{\text{max}} = 1$, the static spin Hall conductivity is in general not quantized. This is due to the Rashba contribution to the SOC proportional to the parameter λ_R . It violates the conservation of the

z -component \hat{S}_z of the spin, because of $[\hat{S}_z, \hat{H}_\zeta(\boldsymbol{\kappa})]_- \sim \lambda_R \neq 0$ with the Hamiltonian (4), except at K or K' points where the commutator vanishes.

As already found in the framework of the Haldane model [339] for spinless electrons and mirror symmetry $\sigma_{xy}^z(0) = -\sigma_{yx}^z(0) = \sigma_{yx}^{-z}(0)$, one derives $\sigma_{xy}^{\pm z}(0) = \pm \frac{e^2}{h}$ [215]. In units of the conductance quantum the static spin Hall conductance computed by means of the Kubo formula (31) can be interpreted as the topological Chern number induced by the Berry curvature (33) in momentum space [340, 341]. In the case of unbuckled graphene it holds $\lambda_R = 0$ (see Table 5). For the low-buckled silicene, germanene, and stanene the Rashba effect is nonzero with $\lambda_R = 0.7, 10.7,$ and 9.5 meV, respectively (see Table 5). The main contribution to the SOC is however due to the term proportional to λ_{SO} . Nevertheless, the quantization of the static spin Hall conductivity is destroyed. The suggestion that a quantum spin Hall phase, as demonstrated by the topological invariant $Z_2 = 1$ for the Xenes, is characterized by a quantized spin Hall conductance is not true. Rather, the conductance value is slightly modified. According to (37) the value e^2/h is reduced by the Rashba SOC. However, the Rashba effect on Xenes is small because of the small ratios $a\lambda_R/\hbar v_F = 0.07$ (silicene), 1.43 (germanene), and 1.40 (stanene) $\times 10^{-2}$ taking the parameters from Table 5. Consequently, the influence of the intrinsic Rashba SOC on the spin Hall conductivity (36) is negligible. This fact explains the observation of nearly quantized static spin Hall conductivities, which are computed *ab initio* within the independent-particle approximation, at least for pure and iodinated germanene, in Fig. 54. The violation of the quantization of the spin Hall conductivity $\sigma_{xy}^z(0)$ is also discussed taking canted spin textures into account [342].

5.3.3. Influence of temperature, doping and gate field

In the computation of the dynamical Hall conductivity $\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega)$ in Fig. 54 a midgap position of the chemical potential of the electrons μ or the Fermi level ε_F (in the low-temperature case) is assumed. Formula (37) for the static conductivity, however, indicates drastic reduction of its absolute value, if the Xene is doped and the chemical potential is moved into bands. For illustration the static spin Hall conductivity of iodinated germanene (GeI) is displayed in Fig. 55 [321] for various temperatures and chemical potentials, whose energy position with respect to the valence and conduction bands is also shown. Practically, the plateau value near $3.874 \times 10^{-5} \Omega^{-1}$ remains hardly modified by varying the temperature. Only for higher temperatures close to room temperature more significant deviations appear. The effect of n -doping is rather weak. Only for the chemical potential deep in the conduction bands a drastic reduction of the conductance value is visible. p -doping and moving the chemical potential closer to or, even, into the Mexican-hat-like valence band lead to a significant reduction of the spin Hall conductivity. Deep in the band even the sign of the conductivity is changed.

In the low-temperature limit this characteristic behavior of the static spin Hall conductivity is almost confirmed for germanene, stanene, iodinated germanene, and fluorostanene with D_{3d} point-group symmetry, which includes the inversion symmetry. It is displayed in Fig. 56. The figure shows that the plateau value of $\sigma_{xy}^z(0) \approx \frac{e^2}{h}$ is nearly correlated with the Fermi level in the gap region of 24.0 (germanene), 73.4 (stanene), 287.7 (fluorostanene), and 310.6 (iodinated germanene) meV in DFT-PBE [87]. However, for the Fermi level ε_F in the band regions the value is substantially reduced from

$\sigma_{xy}^z(0)$. In the plateau regions minor deviations from e^2/h occur. The values 3.83 and 3.84 (in units of $10^{-5}\Omega^{-1}$) computed for germanene and stanene are smaller by less than 1 % in agreement to the discussion of the small Rashba effect in formula (37). The halogenated TIs, GeF and GeI, give values slightly increased by 2 % or 3 %. This increase may be a consequence of the electron transfer from the group-IV basal plane to the F or I atoms and the subsequent modification of SOC.

The influence of an external electric field and the chemical potential on the static spin Hall conductivity can be derived in a similar manner as in (36) and (37) applying the model for low-energy excitations (4). Neglecting the small Rashba contribution one finds [87]

$$\sigma_{xy}^z(0) = \frac{e^2}{h} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=+,-} \text{sgn}(\lambda_s) \frac{1}{\max\left(1, \frac{|\mu|}{|\lambda_s|}\right)} \quad (38)$$

with $\lambda_{\pm} = \lambda_{SO} \pm |U|$. In near agreement with the *ab initio* calculations in Fig. 56 for $U = 0$ expression (38) confirms the plateau in the gap region $|\mu| < \lambda_{SO}$ and a linear decrease proportional to $\lambda_{SO}/|\mu|$, if the chemical potential moves into the conduction or valence bands. For the chemical potential in a midgap position, $\mu = 0$, a step function $\frac{e^2}{h}\Theta(\lambda_{SO} - |U|)$ is derived (see also [343]). This model result is in rough agreement with the *ab initio* findings from Fig. 57a, where the step-like behavior is however smoothed out due to taking the complete band structure and true velocity matrix elements into account.

A vertical electric field not only tunes the fundamental gap of a Xene material as illustrated in Fig. 17b but also destroys the inversion symmetry. In addition, it modifies the effective SOC, which is responsible for the band

gap inversion. The accompanying band gap closing and reopening for field strengths below and above the critical one $F_z^{\text{crit}} = 3.3 \times 10^6$ V/cm are again illustrated in Fig. 57c for germanene [87]. Indeed, for $F_z < F_z^{\text{crit}}$ the system is a TI with $Z_2 = 1$, while for larger field strengths germanene is a trivial insulator with $Z_2 = 0$ (see Fig. 57b). In contrast to E_g and Z_2 the static spin Hall conductivity $\sigma_{xy}^z(0)$ exhibits a monotonous decrease from the value near e^2/h to almost zero for $F_z \rightarrow \infty$ in Fig. 57a. The strongest variation happens in a small range around the critical field strength F_z^{crit} . One of the main reasons for the observations in Fig. 57 may be traced back to the field-induced SOC, which compensates the field-free one, mainly by modifying the term $-\text{grad}V(\mathbf{x})$ by the external field F_z in expression (3). The near quantization of the static spin Hall conductance in Xenes and halogenated Xenes and the possible switching of their topological character by a vertical electric field suggest the application of corresponding nanoribbons in a topological quantum field-effect transistor [224].

6. Summary and perspectives

2D materials in general but, in particular, the Xenes silicene, germanene and stanene, together with their hydrogenated and halogenated derivatives, represent novel classes of quantum materials. Their investigation as atomic monolayers or few-atomic layer systems but, especially, the investigation of their outstanding and exotic properties, are fast growing research directions. In this review we focused on the structural, electronic, optical and topological properties of the Xenes, Xanes and halogenated Xenes such as iodinated germanene and fluorostanene, either as freestanding 2D objects or in interaction

with metallic or nonmetallic substrates.

Silicene, germanene, and stanene are examples of synthetic elemental 2D crystals, similar to graphene. However, there exist no graphite-like bulk analogues from which they can be exfoliated. Their most interesting polymorphs are low-buckled graphene-like structures with honeycomb symmetry. These geometries are dynamically stable. To preserve most of the properties of the freestanding sheets, their fabrication needs physical/chemical growth processes that give rise to only weak interactions between the 2D crystal and the substrate. A van der Waals-type epitaxy on an insulating substrate with wide energy gap could be a favorable approach in the future. Also epitaxial growth by segregation seems to be a reasonable approach. Such heterostructures with weak adsorbate-substrate interaction are also helpful for allowing direct integration of Xenes and their derivatives in electric, optical or photovoltaic devices.

In any case, weak interactions with supporting and/or passivating materials should preserve the intrinsic properties of Xenes, the nearly linear bands – the Dirac cones – and small fundamental gaps due to spin-orbit interaction. The band structures of the Xenes can be significantly modified by adsorbing elements such as hydrogen or halogens. The adsorption leads to nearly completely filled or empty electron shells. The dangling bond orbitals, which contain only one electron, form filled IV-H bonds or rare gas shells around a group-VIIA atom. The resulting mainly covalent bonds, with relatively weak electron transfers from the hydrogen or to the halogen, open huge gaps at the corner points K and K' . As a consequence, the electronic structure near the Γ point gets most interest. The adsorption of hydrogen and group-VII

elements is a playground for manipulating the electronic structure of Xenes.

The almost linear bands near K and K' , and the strong oscillator strengths of corresponding interband transitions for low-energy electronic excitations in Xenes, lead to a constant infrared absorbance, whose value is directly related to the Sommerfeld finestructure constant. For vanishing photon energies this quantity will be however drastically modified by spin-orbit-induced gaps. The supposed instability against the formation of excitons, charge and spin density waves requires deeper many-body studies of the small-gap materials. For higher photon energies, the optical properties are dominated by van Hove singularities due to interband transitions near high-symmetry points as in three dimensions. Thereby, saddle points show strong excitonic effects but no excitonic bound states. The bound excitons become more important at the absorption edges of Xanes and some halogenated Xenes. The oscillator strengths are by a factor 600 larger than in graphane, a fact that suggests the application of Xanes in active optoelectronic devices such as lasers or light-emitting diodes.

While all Xanes are trivial insulators with relatively large quasiparticle gaps, Xenes and partly the halogenated Xenes are topological insulators, whose topological character can however be destroyed by applying vertical electric fields. Their topological invariant Z_2 is directly related to the electronic structure at the center point Γ and three zone boundary points M . It indicates the existence of a quantum spin Hall phase in freestanding objects. The spin Hall conductivity gives seemingly rise to static values close to the reciprocal von Klitzing constant e^2/h , indicating quantization in the case of topological insulators. More detailed studies show that its exact value

is slightly modified by the Rashba part of the spin-orbit interaction and eventually by charge transfer between group-IV and adsorbed atoms. These influences are however almost negligible in Xenes and their topological non-trivial halogen derivatives. After solving the preparation problems, these materials may be applied in topological quantum field-effect transistors.

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Figure Captions

IA	IIA		IIIA		IVA		VA		VIA		VIIA				
1 H Hydrogen 1.008	4 Be Beryllium 9.012	5 B Boron 10.81	6 C Carbon 12.01	7 N Nitrogen 14.01	8 O Oxygen 16.00	9 F Fluorine 18.99	10 Ne	11 Na	12 Mg	13 Al	14 Si	15 P	16 S	17 Cl	18 Ar
	12 Mg Magnesium 24.31	13 Al Aluminum 26.98	14 Si Silicon 28.09	15 P Phosphorus 30.97	16 S Sulfur 32.07	17 Cl Chlorine 35.45	18 Ar	19 K	20 Ca	21 Sc	22 Ti	23 V	24 Cr	25 Mn	26 Fe
	20 Ca Calcium 40.08	31 Ga Gallium 69.72	32 Ge Germanium 72.64	33 As Arsenic 74.92	34 Se Selenium 78.96	35 Br Bromine 79.90	36 Kr	38 Sr	39 Y	40 Zr	41 Nb	42 Mo	43 Tc	44 Ru	45 Rh
	38 Sr Strontium 87.62	49 In Indium 114.82	50 Sn Tin 118.71	51 Sb Antimony 121.76	52 Te Tellurium 127.60	53 I Iodine 126.90	54 Xe	56 Ba	57 La	58 Ce	59 Pr	60 Nd	61 Pm	62 Sm	63 Eu
	56 Ba Barium 137.33	81 Tl Thallium 204.38	82 Pb Lead 207.2	83 Bi Bismuth 208.98	84 Po Polonium 209	85 At	86 Rn	88 Ra	89 Ac	90 Th	91 Pa	92 U	93 Np	94 Pu	95 Am

Figure 1: Excerpt of the Periodic Table with group-IVA elements highlighted in yellow. The elements H, F, Cl, Br, and I used for chemical functionalization are also indicated.

Figure 2: (a) Top and side view of a Xene layer with buckling Δ . (b) Arrangement of atomic layers (here: Xene with thickness δ) in a one-dimensional superlattice, as used for modelling. (c) In-plane projection of the atomic geometry with 2D Bravais lattice and atomic basis. The corresponding hexagonal BZ with indication of important symmetry points Γ , M, and K (K') is shown below.

Figure 3: (a) Silicene layer on hydrogen-passivated Si(111)1×1 surface (Si atoms: blue, H atoms: red). (b) Total energy per silicene atom versus distance layer-substrate in GGA and taking vdW interaction into account. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [51]. Copyright 2013 by John Wiley and Sons.

Figure 4: Total energy of planar (PL), low-buckled (LB) and high-buckled (HB) Si and Ge structures versus lattice constant. The definitions of the buckling and lattice parameters are illustrated in the inset. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [54]. Copyright 2009 by the American Physical Society.

Figure 5: Top and side view of six 2D bonding geometries of Xenes with hexagonal or trigonal symmetry. The lattice parameters indicate the unit cell size (a), the largest (δ_1) and smallest (δ_2) layer buckling. Yellow spheres indicate out-of-plane group-IV atoms. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [65]. Copyright 2015 American Physical Society.

Figure 6: Schematic atomic structure of group-IV sheets (violet balls: Si, Ge, Sn atom) covalent functionalized by F, Cl, Br, I, or H (blue dots). The length of the group-IV atom-atom bond is indicated.

Figure 7: (a) High-resolution STM topograph taken of the 3×3 Si adlayer on Ag(111) 4×4 studying occupied states [105] (credit from A. Resta et al., Aix-Marseille University). (b) Filled state STM image ($U = -1.5$ V) of differently oriented silicene domains on Ag(111). Panel (a) reprinted with permission from Ref. [105]. Copyright 2012 by the American Physical Society. Panel (b) reprinted with permission from Ref. [109]. Copyright 2012 by John Wiley and Sons.

Figure 8: (a) Top and side views of relaxed silicene on the first Ag(111) layer for four model geometries. The uppermost (lower) Si atoms are indicated by red (blue) circles, while Ag atoms appear as gray dots. The crystallographic axes are related to the [111]-oriented cubic Ag substrate. The unit cell of the Si adsorbate is indicated by dashed lines. (b) Computed filled-state STM images. The bias voltage is fixed at -1 V. In the insets, uppermost (intermediate, lowest) Si atoms are indicated by red (yellow, blue) balls. (c) Calculated phase diagram of silicene on Ag(111). The adsorbate formation energy is plotted as a function of the Si chemical potential μ_{Si} with respect to its bulk value. Coverage θ and biaxial strain ε are listed for each phase. The inset shows the formation energy relative to that of the 4×4 structure. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [112]. Copyright 2014 American Physical Society.

Figure 9: High-symmetry orientations and cuts along (a) armchair ($[1120]$) and (b) zigzag ($[1\bar{1}00]$) direction in a LB Xene geometry, whose top and side views are displayed. Denotations correspond to hexagonal Miller, i.e., Bravais, indices [49], where the layer normal is parallel to the $[0001]$ direction.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of silicene adsorbed on (a) Cl-passivated $\text{Si}(111)1 \times 1$ and (b) clean $\text{CaF}_2(111)1 \times 1$ surface. Si atoms: blue, Cl: green, Ca: yellow, F: red. Copyright 2014 IOP Publishing Ltd. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [154]. All rights reserved.

Figure 11: Xene layer stacked on graphene at C-terminated SiC. Group-IV (e.g. silicon), carbon, and hydrogen atoms are displayed as red, green, blue, and white circles. The layer distances d and the buckling parameters Δ are indicated. From Ref. [88].

Figure 12: Top (a) and side (b) view of 3×3 silicene on 2×2 kagome Al_2O_3 . Si atoms: blue, Al: violet, O: red. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [179]. Copyright 2019 American Physical Society.

Figure 13: Experimental (STM) (a) and theoretical (b) Moiré pattern of a twisted bilayer graphene rotated by 3.28° and 3.3° , respectively, with respect to each other. The theoretical LDA lattice parameter of the unit cell, represented by blue dashed lines in (b), is 4.28 nm, in good agreement with the experimental result of 4.4 nm. While the experimental image is obtained by STM at a bias $U = 0.2$ V, the theoretical one is derived as spatial distribution of the carbon atoms (gray circles) in the two atomic layers. (a) Reproduced with permission from Ref. [191]. Copyright 2012 by the American Physical Society. (b) Reprinted with permission from Ref. [110]. Copyright 2016 American Chemical Society.

Figure 14: Kohn-Sham band structure of silicene versus the 2D hexagonal BZ with the high-symmetry points Γ , M, K, and K'. The Fermi level is used to define the energy zero and, therefore, the position of the Dirac points. Adapted and reproduced from Ref. [192].

Figure 15: (a) Quasiparticle GW (red lines) and DFT-PBE (black lines) band structures of graphene. The Fermi level is taken as energy zero. Adapted from Supplementary Material to Ref. [201]. (b) HSE (red) and DFT-GGA (blue dashed) bands of germanene with SOC. Copyright 2013 IOP Publishing Ltd. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [17]. All rights reserved.

Figure 16: QP band structures (red lines) of (a) graphene, (b) silicene, (c) germanene, and (d) stanene along high-symmetry lines ΓM , MK , and $K\Gamma$ of the 2D hexagonal BZ (see Fig. 2c) using the HSE06 functional including SOC. The insets show a magnification of the bands and band gaps around the Dirac points together with the bands without SOC (black lines). Copyright 2013 IOP Publishing Ltd. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [17]. All rights reserved.

Figure 17: (a) Application of a gate field in normal direction on buckled germanene. The wave functions of the Dirac point at K or K' are indicated. (b) Energy gap of germanene versus the applied electric field from generalized KS eigenvalues. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [226]. Copyright 2014 American Physical Society.

Figure 18: Band structure of germanene under influence of an external field. (a) $F_z = 0$, (b) $F_z = 2 \times 10^6$ V/cm, (c) $F_z = 3 \times 10^6$ V/cm, and (d) $F_z = 5 \times 10^6$ V/cm with (c) close to the critical field strength. Red, green, and blue circles depict relative contributions from s , p_{xy} , and p_z orbitals, respectively. The valence-band maximum at K defines the energy zero. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [87]. Copyright 2019 American Physical Society.

Figure 19: Field-modified total density of states (8) near the Dirac point at zero energy.

Figure 20: Quasiparticle band structures (black lines) of graphane, silicane, germanane (left panels), and stanane (right panel) in chairlike geometry. In the latter case, SOC is also taken into account. The DFT-LDA bands are with SOC (red lines) and without SOC (red-dashed lines), respectively. The valence band maximum is taken as energy zero. In left panels the horizontal red-dashed line indicates the vacuum level. Arrows display fundamental gaps. Left panels reproduced with permission from Ref. [91]. Right panel adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [93]. Article published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License.

Figure 21: Square of KS wave functions at Γ of graphane. (a) Uppermost valence band, (b) lowest conduction band, and (c) second lowest conduction band. Colors indicate the probability strength.

Figure 22: Atom-projected (P) DOS of graphane, silicane, and germanane around the fundamental gap. Solid red (black dashed) line describes the projection onto group-IV (H) contributions. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [91].

Figure 23: QP band structure of silicographene (a) and silicographane (b). The top of the valence band is used as energy zero. The red and green horizontal lines indicate the different vacuum levels. The inset in (b) shows the wave function square at Γ for the lowest conduction band. Reprinted from Ref. [78], with permission of AIP Publishing.

Figure 25: ARPES intensity map of (a) 3×3 silicene on 4×4 Ag(111) along the $K_{Ag}\Gamma$ direction through the silicene K_{Si} point as indicated by the horizontal arrow in the BZs and (b) $\sqrt{27}\times\sqrt{27}$ germanene on 8×8 Au(111) along the ΓK_{Au} line of the metal substrate. Dirac cones around the K_{Au} point and the zone center Γ are visible. The BZ subfigure shows that the K points of the small BZs coincide with K_{Au} points, while K and K' points of the 1×1 germanene BZ are folded onto Γ points of the smaller BZs. (a) Reproduced from Ref. [105]. Copyright 2012 by the American Physical Society. (b) Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [134]. Article published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License.

Figure 26: DFT band structure of the 3×3 silicene/ 4×4 Ag(111) system. Left: Bands of silicene-covered silver slab around the Γ point of the joint BZ, onto which the K point of the 1×1 BZ is folded. Middle: Bands of Si overlayer peeled-off from the substrate. Si p_z (p_{xy}) orbitals are indicated by red (blue) lines, while Ag-derived bands are represented as gray lines. Right: BZ folding. The two 1×1 BZs together with the small 2D BZs of the overlayer system. Adapted from Ref. [192].

Figure 27: DFT band structures of the Si/Ag(111)4 \times 4 surface close to the K point of 1 \times 1 silicene along the $[\bar{1}10]$, i.e., k_x , direction. Red circles denote bands with significant Si character. Black dashed lines suggest linear Si-derived bands near K. Gray solid lines represent Ag(111)-derived (a) or Ag-projected (b) bands. The vacuum level is taken as energy zero, while the horizontal black lines indicate the Fermi level. (c) Wave function square of the band state close to the apex of the apparent cone. Reprinted from Ref. [116], with permission of AIP Publishing.

Figure 28: Band structure of silicene (without SOC) on insulating substrates. (a) 3×3 silicene on 2×2 Al_2O_3 monolayer in GW quality [179], (b) 1×1 silicene on 1×1 $\text{CaF}_2(111)$ in DFT-GGA [154]. Bands are displayed as red or black lines. Projected CaF_2 bands are indicated in the shaded regions. The Fermi level is taken as energy zero. (a) Reproduced with permission from Ref. [179]. (b) Copyright 2014 IOP Publishing Ltd. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [154]. All rights reserved.

Figure 29: Schematic illustrations of a SDRS study of an isotropic 2D crystal on a substrate, e.g. $\text{Si}/\text{Ag}(111)$, (left panel) with light and nearly normal incidence and a RAS experiment on an anisotropic overlayer, e.g. $\text{Si}/\text{Ag}(110)$ (right panel).

Figure 30: (a, c) Real and (b, d) imaginary parts of the optical conductivity of graphene and silicene, respectively, in a wide range of photon energies. In-plane component $\sigma_{2D}^{\parallel}(\omega)$: black lines, out-of-plane component $\sigma_{2D}^{\perp}(\omega)$: red lines. The spectra are normalized to the dc conductivity $\sigma_0 = \frac{e^2}{4\hbar} = \frac{c}{4}\alpha$ with $\alpha = \frac{e^2}{\hbar c}$ as the Sommerfeld fine structure constant. The underlying electronic structure results from DFT-GGA. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [261]. Copyright 2016 American Physical Society.

Figure 31: Light propagation in a three layer system consisting of a 2D sheet (in red) with thickness $\delta \rightarrow 0$ as well as vacuum and a dielectric or metal as substrate.

Figure 32: Frequency dependence of reflectance $R(\omega)$ (black line), transmittance $T(\omega)$, more precisely $T(\omega) - 1$ (green line), and absorbance $A(\omega)$ (red line) of (a) graphene, (b) silicene, (c) germanene, and (d) stanene for normal incidence. The calculations are performed in the framework of the hybrid functional HSE06. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [19]. Article published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) Licence.

Figure 33: Interband transition energies along high-symmetry lines in the BZ of graphene, silicene, and germanene. The resulting JDOS is also displayed [in units of $(\text{eV})^{-1}$]. All quantities in DFT-GGA quality. The red-dashed horizontal lines indicate energies of van Hove singularities. Adapted and reproduced from Ref. [268], with permission of AIP Publishing.

Figure 34: (a) Band energies near a Dirac point normalized in units of $\hbar v_F \pi / a$. (b) Normalized in-plane transition matrix elements of the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions along high-symmetry lines near the BZ boundary. Graphene: black solid line, silicene: red-dashed line, and germanene: blue-dotted line. Figures (a) and (b) adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [267]. Copyright 2013 American Physical Society. Wave-function squares in silicene for the highest occupied π state (c) and the lowest empty π^* state (d) at K. The atomic positions in the Si sheet indicate the buckled honeycomb geometry.

Figure 35: *Ab initio* calculated optical absorbance of graphene (black solid line), silicene (red dashed line), and germanene (blue dotted line) (a) for small photon energies and (b) in wider energy range. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [267]. Copyright 2013 American Physical Society.

Figure 36: (a) Low-energy conductivity and (b) optical matrix element near K of germanene with (red line) and without (black line) SOC. All quantities are computed within the HSE06 approach. Copyright 2013 IOP Publishing Ltd. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [17]. All rights reserved.

Figure 37: (a) Band structure and (b) real part of the in-plane optical conductivity calculated in independent-particle approximation (black line) for Bernal-stacked bilayer graphene. For comparison, the normalized absorption (red line) of two noninteracting graphene layers is displayed, too. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [276]. Copyright 2018 Springer Nature.

Figure 38: Geometries (a, b), band structures (c, d), and real parts of the in-plane optical conductivity (e, f) of silicene bilayers with AA (a, c, e) and AB (b, d, f) stacking. In (e) and (f) the results are compared with the doubled conductivity of isolated silicene sheets. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [276]. Copyright 2018 Springer Nature.

Figure 39: Quadrilayer heterostructure of silicene/ Al_2O_3 /silicene/ Al_2O_3 . (a) Side view. Notations are the same as in Fig. 12. (b) DFT band structure. Red: band states localized on silicene; blue: alumina and hybridized states. The zero energy is set at the Fermi level. (c) Absorbance: Spectrum of quadrilayer (black line). Spectrum of twice the bilayer heterostructure (cyan line). Spectrum of twice the freestanding silicene (magenta line). Figures (b) and (c) adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [179]. Copyright 2019 American Physical Society.

Figure 40: Field dependence of the ratio of exciton binding energy to band gap for free-standing biased silicene (red line), germanene (blue line), and stanene (purple line). The binding energies have been calculated for Wannier-Mott excitons (26), where the electron-hole attraction is described by the Rytova-Keldysh potential (25). The horizontal line indicates the critical value, that separates the possibility of an EI and a conventional semiconductor. Adapted and reprinted with permission from Ref. [302]. Copyright 2019 Elsevier.

Figure 41: Real (a) and imaginary (b) part of the in-plane conductivity of freestanding silicene calculated within three different approaches to many-body effects. Black lines: IPA using the DFT-GGA electronic structure in (10); red lines: IQPA using the G_0W_0 QP corrections in (10); and green line: G_0W_0 -BSE treatment (12) in (11) including both QP and excitonic effects. The optical conductivity is plotted in units of $\sigma_0 = e^2/(4\hbar)$. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [276]. Copyright 2018 Springer Nature.

Figure 42: Real part of the in-plane optical conductivity calculated within DFT-GGA for freestanding silicene (black solid line) and 3×3 silicene peeled off from the 4×4 Ag(111) substrate (red dashed line). Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [255]. Copyright 2018 American Physical Society.

Figure 43: (a) Low-temperature absorption spectrum of germanane measured by diffuse reflectance absorption spectroscopy. The gap determination is indicated by the solid red lines. (b) Temperature dependence of absorption edge. Adapted with permission from Ref. [98]. Copyright 2013 American Chemical Society.

Figure 44: (a) Series of bound exciton states in the absorption of hydrogenated group-IV sheet crystals with honeycomb symmetry below the fundamental QP gap (vertical dashed line). The graphane spectrum has been enhanced by a factor 600. (b) Two-particle wave function of the lowest-energy exciton with the hole fixed in the center of a IV-IV bond. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [91].

Figure 45: In-plane absorption spectrum of stanane in GW-BSE with SOC. For comparison also spectra without SOC and without excitonic effects in independent-QP approach are shown. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [93]. Article published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License.

Figure 46: Comparison of exciton binding energies of several 2D honeycomb-based materials calculated *ab initio* by solving the BSE (black line) and by solving a 2D exciton model within effective-mass approximation and Rytova-Keldysh screened potential (25) (red line). Reproduced with permission from Ref. [308]. Article published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License.

Figure 47: (a) Calculated absorption spectrum of fluorographane in independent-QP (red line) and GW-BSE (black line) approach. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [309]. Copyright 2013 American Physical Society. (b) Measured optical transparency change of graphene due to fluorination. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [79]. Copyright 2010, John Wiley and Sons.

Figure 48: (a) 2D DFT-PBE band structure of GeI. The Fermi level without doping defines the energy zero. (b) Schematic presentation of the H-passivated edge of a zigzag GeI nanoribbon (blue: Ge, purple: I, white: H). (c) 1D band structure of a zigzag GeI nanoribbon. The folded 2D band structure is represented by blue regions, while the red lines indicate the bands of spin-polarized topological states. (d) Localization of topological edge states of a H-passivated zigzag edge of a pure germanene nanoribbon. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Refs. [226, 321]. Copyright 2014, 2016 American Physical Society.

Figure 49: (a) Γ and M TRIM points (red dots) in hexagonal BZ. The basis vectors \mathbf{b}_1 and \mathbf{b}_2 of the reciprocal lattice are also displayed. (b) Occupied bands of germanene along high-symmetry lines. The parities of the band states at TRIM points are indicated. Adapted and reproduced from Ref. [88].

Figure 50: HSE band structures of (a) iodinated germanene, (b) germanene, and (c) germanane. The parities of the occupied bands at TRIM points are indicated. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [239]. Copyright 2016 American Physical Society.

Figure 51: Evolution of Wannier charge centers along the ΓM line in germanene under applied electric field slightly below (left panel) and above (right panel) of the critical field strength. The change of the topological character is obvious. From [88].

Figure 52: Evolution of Wannier charge centers along a ΓM line for (a) stanene on H-passivated SiC substrate and (b) freestanding iodinated germanene. The red lines in (a) indicate phases which are derived for mainly stanene-like bands. Adapted from Ref. [88].

Figure 53: Schematic representation of a SOC-induced spin current j_x^z by the current j_y due to the electric field component F_y in a 2D honeycomb crystal, assuming a spin component in normal z -direction.

Figure 54: Spin Hall conductivity $\sigma_{xy}^z(\omega) \equiv \sigma_{xy}^{\text{sH}}(\omega)$ (real part: solid lines, imaginary part: dashed lines) for (a) iodinated germanene, (b) pure germanene, and (c) hydrogenated germanene as a function of the photon energy. The broadening parameter is varied with $\eta = 30$ meV (blue), 40 meV (green), 50 meV (red), and 100 meV (black) in (a) and (c). In (b): $\eta = 1$ meV (blue), $\eta = 3$ meV (green), 5 meV (red), and 10 meV (black). Reproduced with permission from Ref. [239]. Copyright 2016 American Physical Society.

Figure 55: Static spin Hall conductivity of iodinated germanene versus position of the chemical potential indicated by the energy scale in the lower panel. The sample temperature is varied from $T = 0\text{K}$ (red line), 30K (green line), 100K (blue line) to 300K (black line). In order to illustrate the doping level, the correspondingly aligned band structure is displayed in the upper panel. Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [321]. Copyright 2016 American Physical Society.

Figure 56: Static spin Hall conductivity versus Fermi level for (a) germanene, (b) stanene, (c) fluorostanene, and (d) GeI. The horizontal blue-dotted line illustrates the quantum e^2/h . The hatched gray region indicates the band gap. Zero Fermi level is chosen in a midgap position. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [87]. Copyright 2019 American Physical Society.

Figure 57: (a) Static spin Hall conductivity (electron chemical potential μ in midgap position), (b) Z_2 invariant, and (c) band gap as a function of the applied vertical electric field on germanene. The horizontal blue-dotted line illustrates the quantized value e^2/h . Adapted and reproduced with permission from Ref. [87]. Copyright 2019 American Physical Society.